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List of Abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease 2019
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
H2020	European Commission Framework Programme Horizon 2020
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
RI	Research Infrastructure
RTD	Research and Technological Development
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
TA	Trans-national Access
UK	United Kingdom
USA	United States of America
USP	User Selection Panel
VA	Virtual Access

Executive Summary

Following the way paved by its predecessor ERIGrid, the main goal of the ERIGrid 2.0 project was to provide on-site and remote lab access to an integrated Research Infrastructure, operated at 21 distributed installations in 11 countries. The ERIGrid 2.0 lab access programme was mainly offered to the European research community, where the need to investigate and validate complex smart grid configurations and smart energy systems is essential.

This document summarises the Laboratory Access or short “Lab Access” (i.e., “Trans-national Access”) activity performed in ERIGrid 2.0 from October 2020, when the 1st call for lab access proposals was launched, until the end of the project in April 2025. The report compiles the different calls, proposals received, and their evaluation by the User Selection Panel. Based on this information, an analysis of the degree of accomplishment of the access provision at the partner and project levels is carried out against the demanding access objectives of the project.

In addition, ERIGrid 2.0 offered the possibility of Virtual Access to researchers around the world: 10 databases, real-time data or simulation platforms have been made available online and free of charge. This report compiles and evaluates available statistics and metrics on the usage of these online services until April 2025.

1 Introduction

ERIGrid 2.0 is a pan-European Research Infrastructure (RI), which integrates 21 first-class laboratories located in 11 European countries, and aims at placing this RI at the disposal of the European research community (and also of the international one, with some limitations), including industrial organisations. The project offered a five-year access programme supported by the European Commission (EC) through the European Commission Framework Programme Horizon 2020 (H2020).

ERIGrid 2.0 offered free of charge access to its laboratories and associated services to all interested researchers in the domains of smart grids and smart energy systems, along with logistical, technological and scientific support for their experimental research.

At the same time, ERIGrid 2.0 provided the opportunity to access 10 virtual facilities (databases, real-time data or simulation platforms) free of charge, to researchers worldwide through the so-called Virtual Access (VA) modality.

This document compiles and summarizes the lab access (i.e., Trans-national Access (TA)) and VA provision during the duration of the access programme in ERIGrid 2.0 (October 2020 – April 2025), and updates a previous assessment performed in the middle of it (i.e., Deliverable D6.5 (*D-NA5.3a Evaluation of the Access Provision Programme*, 2023)).

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

The objective of this deliverable is to report on the lab access and VA activities performed in ERIGrid 2.0 from its beginning in April 2020 until April 2025. The procedures and conditions of the access schemes in ERIGrid 2.0 have been formulated in Deliverable D6.1 (*D-NA5.1 Specification of the Trans-national Access and Virtual Access Programmes*, 2021) linked to Call 1 for lab access proposals and the launching of the VA services.

This report describes from the administrative point of view the different calls, the proposals received, their evaluation by the User Selection Panel (USP), and their final status regarding lab implementation; based on this information, the document presents the degree of accomplishment of the lab access provision at individual RI and project levels, jointly with several metrics and statistics on the use of the VA online services.

The scientific achievements and lessons learned coming from the lab implementations of the different user projects are out of the scope of this document and are reported in Deliverables D7.1 (*D-TA1.1 Transient Power System Dynamics and Control Validation Trans-national Access Scientific Highlights and Lessons Learned*, 2025) and Deliverable D8.1 (*D-TA2.1 Smart Energy Systems Trans-national Access Scientific Highlights and Lessons Learned*, 2025).

1.2 Structure of the Document

This document is organized as follows: After an executive summary, an introduction on the purpose, scope and structure of the report is provided; the core of the document includes six sections: Section 2 summarises the call timeline and deadlines, Section 3 compiles the proposals received in the different calls for lab access and the final implementation status in the lab, Section 4 details the evaluation process results of the received proposals performed by the USP, Section 5 mentions the user workshops organised during the lifetime of ERIGrid 2.0 for disseminating the outcomes of the access programme, and finally Section 6 and Section 7

assess the final provision of lab access and VA, respectively. The report ends with the relevant conclusions in Section 8 and an Appendix containing an example of the proposal review report.

2 Laboratory Access Process

As described in Deliverable D6.1 (*D-NA5.1 Specification of the Trans-national Access and Virtual Access Programmes, 2021*), the general call timeline is shown in Figure 1. As a reference, the duration of the call and the associated user access lasted for around 12 months, with the following main periods:

- The call remained open for 3 months.
- The proposals received were evaluated by an independent USP within 1 month (2 months maximum) after the closing date of each call.
- The access period had to be allocated within 6 months after acceptance of the proposal, with a typical duration of 1-4 weeks (and limited to a maximum of 3 months if well justified). The implementation could be split into 2 phases (2 access periods) in the lab, if necessary, but not more.
- After finishing the lab access, there was a two-month time limit for the user group to carry out the mandatory reporting of the project experiments.

Figure 1: Lab access call reference timeline.

In ERIGrid 2.0, lab access calls have been launched every 4 months, with the same reference timeline as outlined in Figure 1. The call sequence for the first three calls is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Sequence of lab access calls.

The reference deadlines of the above steps in the access process turned out to be challenging, based on the accumulated experience in the project. Some flexibility was provided by ERIGrid 2.0 for the sake of maximising the access provision, especially considering the Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic restrictions of the first two years of the project, including lockdown periods and restricted access to lab services.

3 Calls for Laboratory Access

The lab access in ERIGrid 2.0 has been implemented through successive public calls, published every 4 months. This report covers the 13 calls for lab access proposals. The timeline of the calls is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Timeline of lab access calls.

A total of 13 calls for lab access proposals have been launched during ERIGrid 2.0. The lab implementation of all approved user projects has been extended until the last month of the project, aiming at maximising the provided access to users.

A summary of the assessment of the lab access user proposals in the launched calls is the following:

- *1st Call for Lab Access Proposals (05/10/2020 – 31/12/2020)*: 11 proposals received, 2 rejected by the USP, 9 accepted for lab implementation, 2 proposals withdrawn by the user afterwards.
- *2nd Call for Lab Access Proposals (01/02/2021 – 30/04/2021)*: 13 proposals received, 2 rejected by the USP, 11 accepted for lab implementation, 2 proposals withdrawn by the user afterwards.
- *3rd Call for Lab Access Proposals (01/06/2021 – 31/08/2021)*: 3 proposals received, 3 accepted for lab implementation.
- *4th Call for Lab Access Proposals (01/10/2021 – 31/12/2021)*: 16 proposals received, 3 rejected by the USP, 2 unfeasible, 11 accepted for lab implementation, 3 proposals withdrawn by the user afterwards.
- *5th Call for Lab Access Proposals (01/02/2022 – 30/04/2022)*: 11 proposals received, 11 accepted for lab implementation, 1 proposal withdrawn by the user afterwards.
- *6th Call for Lab Access Proposals (01/06/2022 – 31/08/2022)*: 6 proposals received, 1 unfeasible, 5 accepted for lab implementation, 1 proposal withdrawn by the user afterwards.
- *7th Call for Lab Access Proposals (01/10/2022 – 31/12/2022)*: 25 proposals received, 2 rejected by the USP, 2 rejected due to non-European Union (EU) limitation, 21 accepted for lab implementation, 4 proposals withdrawn by the user afterwards.
- *8th Call for Lab Access Proposals (01/02/2023 – 30/04/2023)*: 16 proposals received, 1

rejected by the USP, 6 rejected due to non-EU limitation, 9 accepted for lab implementation.

- *9th Call for Lab Access Proposals (01/06/2023 – 31/08/2023)*: 5 proposals received, 1 rejected by the USP, 4 accepted for lab implementation.
- *10th Call for Lab Access Proposals (01/10/2023 – 31/12/2023)*: 16 proposals received, 1 rejected due to non-EU limitation, 15 accepted for lab implementation.
- *11th Call for Lab Access Proposals (10/01/2024 – 31/03/2024)*: 6 proposals received, 1 rejected due to non-EU limitation, 5 accepted for lab implementation, 1 proposal withdrawn by the user afterwards.
- *12th Call for Lab Access Proposals (01/04/2024 – 30/06/2024)*: 5 proposals received, 5 accepted for lab implementation.
- *13th Call for Lab Access Proposals (01/07/2024 – 30/09/2024)*: 14 proposals received, 1 unfeasible, 13 accepted for lab implementation, 1 proposal withdrawn by the user afterwards.

This means that 147 user proposals have been received in the above calls (11.3 proposals per call on average); 106 projects have been finally implemented in the related RIs (i.e., labs), providing 1,677 access days to 224 users.

Once the access was completed at the RIs, the user groups (except Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs)) had to prepare a Technical Report of the implemented project. This mandatory document contains the first scientific output on the experiment implementation and results generated by the users, who utilised the ERIGrid 2.0 lab access opportunity.

Most reports for the completed projects have already been received from the users; the remaining reports correspond mainly to the projects implemented during the last three months of ERIGrid 2.0. All documents are kept in the project's internal repository and uploaded to the project's website¹ and Zenodo's ERIGrid 2.0 Community² for public availability.

3.1 1st Call for Lab Access Proposals (05/10/2020 – 31/12/2020)

This section compiles the proposals received in the 1st Call for lab access proposals launched from 5th October 2020 to 31st December 2020. For each proposal, the title, user organisation/s, host infrastructure/s and access status are presented.

The following list provides an executive summary of the call outcomes:

- 11 proposals received, 2 not accepted by the USP, 2 withdrawn by the user.
- Type of organisation: 8 from Universities + 3 from Industry (SME and other profit private organisations).
- Access duration: 5-27 access days, 13 access days (average).
- User Groups from:
 - EU: 3 proposals (Spain, Italy, Denmark).

¹<https://erigrd2.eu/user-projects>

²<https://zenodo.org/communities/erigrd2>

- Associated Countries: 4 proposals (Serbia, Turkey, Switzerland, United Kingdom (UK)).
- Non-EU: 4 proposals (United States of America (USA), India, Pakistan).

1	PMU-FFR	Validation of PMU based Fast Frequency Response Control Scheme in P-HIL Environment				
		User Group Organisations:	University of Belgrade		Serbia	
		Host Research Installation:	Dynamic Power Systems Laboratory (UST)			
		Access Status:	Withdrawn by user		--- users	
					--- access days	
		Remote Access		--- access days		
		Industry user project:	No	--- industry users		
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No			

2	DEFINIT 2.0	DEcentralized Fault IdeNtification for distribution grids using a limited number of measurements of LV voltage and current: development and performance assessment				
		User Group Organisations:	Depsys		Switzerland	
		Host Research Installation:	Power Networks Demonstration Centre (UST)			
		Access Status:	Completed		2 users	
					5 access days	
		Remote Access		--- access days		
Industry user project:	Yes	DEPSYS SA www.depsys.com		2 industry users		
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No			

3	COLOUR-POWER	Wavelet-Transform based Signal Processing for the Validation of Power Flow Tracing Approach				
		User Group Organisations:	University of Glasgow University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria		UK Spain	
		Host Research Installation:	Distributed Energy Resources Test Facility (RSE)			
		Access Status:	Completed		2 users	
					10 access days	
		Remote Access		--- access days		
Industry user project:	No	--- industry users				
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No			

4	AutonoM	Autonomous Microgrid Controller				
		User Group Organisations:	Middle East Technical University		Turkey	
		Host Research Installation:	SYSLAB and Energy Systems Simulation Lab (DTU)			
		Access Status:	Completed		3 users	
					10 access days	
		Remote Access		--- access days		
Industry user project:	No	--- industry users				
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No			

5	POLARIS	Power sharing for Low-inertia Assets in Renewable-based Inverter Systems				
		User Group Organisations:		Virginia Tech		USA
		Host Research Installation:		Dynamic Power Systems Laboratory (UST)		
		Access Status:		Completed		1 user
						15 access days
				Remote Access		--- access days
		Industry user project:	No			--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No			
6	SES-MGES	Stochastic Multi-objective Scheduling of Smart Energy System considering Multi-generation Energy Storage				
		User Group Organisations:		Aalborg University		Denmark
		Host Research Installation:		SESA-Lab (OFFIS)		
		Access Status:		Completed		1 user
						27 access days
				Remote Access		--- access days
		Industry user project:	No			--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No			
7	Hytechnet	Multi-criteria evaluation of hydrogen technologies for the design of distribution networks based on renewable energy				
		User Group Organisations:		H2Cloud Energy		Spain
		Host Research Installation:		Electrical Sustainable Power Lab (TU Delft)		
		Access Status:		Withdrawn by user		--- users
						--- access days
				Remote Access		--- access days
		Industry user project:	Yes	H2Cloud Energy www.h2cloudenergy.com		--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No			
8	M-ECHall	Renewable Energy Community "Energy City Hall" of the City of Magliano Alpi (Italy)				
		User Group Organisations:		Energy City Hall		Italy
		Host Research Installation:		Smart Grid Interoperability Lab in Ispra, IT (JRC, EC)		
		Access Status:		Completed		2 users
						9 access days
				Remote Access		--- access days
		Industry user project:	Yes	Studio Blangetti www.studioblangetti.it		2 industry users
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No			
9	BAMLEV	Electric Vehicle Battery Degradation Analysis and Estimation using Machine Learning Techniques				
		User Group Organisations:		Lahore University of Management Sciences		Pakistan
		Host Research Installation:		---		
		Access Status:		Not approved by USP		--- users
						--- access days
				Remote Access		--- access days
		Industry user project:	No			--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No			

10	RT-SimVal	Real-time simulation and validation of integrated Fault classification and Section Identification (IFCSI) Method in Distribution Network (with and without DG integration) for faster service restoration using real-time measurements and state estimation of CFPIs				
		User Group Organisations:		University of Petroleum and Energy Studies		India
		Host Research Installation:		Electrical Sustainable Power Lab (TU Delft)		
		Access Status:		Completed		1 user
						15 access days
				Remote Access		--- access days
		Industry user project:	No			--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No			
11	OEM-MGR	Optimal Energy Management of Micro Grids with V2G and Renewables				
		User Group Organisations:		Lahore University of Management Sciences		Pakistan
		Host Research Installation:		---		
		Access Status:		Not approved by USP		--- users
						--- access days
				Remote Access		--- access days
		Industry user project:	No			--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No			

3.2 2nd Call for Lab Access Proposals (01/02/2021 – 30/04/2021)

This section compiles the proposals received in the 2nd Call for lab access proposals launched from 1st February 2021 to 30th April 2021. For each proposal, the title, user organisation/s, host infrastructure/s and access status are presented.

The following list provides an executive summary of the call outcomes:

- 13 proposals received, 2 not accepted by the USP, 2 withdrawn by the user.
- Type of organisation: 11 from Universities + 2 from Research Organisations.
- Access duration: 8-30 access days, 13 access days (average).
- User Groups from:
 - EU: 8 proposals (Finland, Austria, Malta/Cyprus, France, Germany, Poland).
 - Associated Countries: 2 proposals (Norway, UK).
 - Non-EU: 3 proposals (Russia, India).

1	DPSSEC	<i>Distributed power system state estimation and cybersecurity in smart grid</i>					
		User Group Organisations:	Skolkovo institute of science and technology		Russia		
		Host Research Installation:	---				
		Access Status:	Not approved by USP			--- users	
			Remote Access			--- access days	
		Industry user project:	No				--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No				

2	PROOF	<i>Adaptive protection for microgrids based on communication</i>					
		User Group Organisations:	Lappeenranta University of Technology (LUT)		Finland		
		Host Research Installation:	Electric Energy Systems Laboratory (ICCS-NTUA)				
		Access Status:	Completed			3 users	
			Remote Access			--- access days	
		Industry user project:	No				--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No				

3	VOIDIP	<i>Enabling LVRT-HVRT functions and Power Curtailment in Microgrid using Disturbance Identification and Islanding Information with Micro PMU</i>					
		User Group Organisations:	Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur		India		
		Host Research Installation:	Electrical Sustainable Power Lab (TU Delft)				
		Access Status:	Withdrawn by user			--- users	
			Remote Access			--- access days	
		Industry user project:	No				--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No				

4	DeMaDsVal	<i>Data Driven Detection of Malfunctioning Devices in Power Distribution Systems Validation</i>					
		User Group Organisations:	Austrian Institute of Technology, AIT		Austria		
		Host Research Installation:	Power Networks Demonstration Centre (UST)				
		Access Status:	Completed			1 user	
			Remote Access			--- access days	
		Industry user project:	No				--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	Yes	19 access days			

5	GRIDPV100	<i>Innovative RES Solutions for 100% RES Systems</i>					
		User Group Organisations:	Malta College of Arts, Science and Technology FOSS Research Centre for Sustainable Energy		Malta Cyprus		
		Host Research Installation:	Smart Electricity Systems and Technologies Laboratory (AIT)				
		Access Status:	Completed			2 users	
			Remote Access			30 access days	
		Industry user project:	No				--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	Yes	27 access days			

6	DynOMO	Dynamic Interaction of Offshore Wind Farm Through MTDC Network with Onshore AC Grid				
		User Group Organisations:	Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur		India	
		Host Research Installation:	---			
		Access Status:	Not approved by USP		--- users	
			Remote Access		--- access days	
		Industry user project:	No			--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No			
7	SIM HES-OFF	Simulation Platform for Hybrid Energy Systems in Offshore Oil & Gas Installations				
		User Group Organisations:	NTNU – Dept. Electric Power Engineering (IEL)		Norway	
		Host Research Installation:	Real-Time Lab (RWTH Aachen University)			
		Access Status:	Completed		1 user	
			Remote Access		--- access days	
		Industry user project:	No			--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No			
8	PPiF	Primary Support in Finland				
		User Group Organisations:	Grenoble INP		France	
		Host Research Installation:	Intelligent Energy Testbed (VTT)			
		Access Status:	Completed		2 users	
			Remote Access		11 access days	
		Industry user project:	No			--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No			
9	Open-CAN-Verter	Study of the expansion of microgrids using software defined power converters and open CAN-based communication architecture				
		User Group Organisations:	LAAS CNRS, University of Toulouse Libre Solar Technologies GmbH		France Germany	
		Host Research Installation:	Electric Energy Systems Laboratory (ICCS-NTUA)			
		Access Status:	Completed		3 users	
			Remote Access		--- access days	
		Industry user project:	Yes	Libre Solar Technologies GmbH https://libre.solar		1 industry user
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No			
10	VaFlexPot	Validation of a flexibility potential model and network use cases				
		User Group Organisations:	TU Dortmund University		Germany	
		Host Research Installation:	SYSLAB and Energy Systems Simulation Lab (DTU)			
		Access Status:	Completed		1 user	
			Remote Access		9 access days	
Industry user project:	No			--- industry users		

11	CREAM	<i>Cascade Reduction with an Epidemic Analysis Method</i>				
		User Group Organisations:		University of Sussex		UK
		Host Research Installation:		Real-Time Lab (RWTH Aachen University)		
		Access Status:		Withdrawn by user		--- users
				Remote Access		--- access days
		Industry user project:		No		--- industry users
Non-EU user project:		No		Internal-TA:	No	

12	PVInPS	<i>Photovoltaics Integration in Distributed Power Systems</i>				
		User Group Organisations:		AGH University of Science and Technology		Poland
		Host Research Installation:		Smart Electricity Systems and Technologies Laboratory (AIT) Flex Power Grid Laboratory (KEMA Labs) Low Voltage Experimental Microgrid Lab (FOSS-UCY)		
		Access Status:		Completed		4 users
				Remote Access		25 access days
		Industry user project:		No		--- access days
Non-EU user project:		No		Internal-TA:	No	
				--- industry users		

13	resiMG	<i>Resilience-oriented Microgrid Control and Protection</i>				
		User Group Organisations:		Hochschule Darmstadt University of Applied Sciences		Germany
		Host Research Installation:		Electric Energy Systems Laboratory (ICCS-NTUA)		
		Access Status:		Completed		2 users
				Remote Access		8 access days
		Industry user project:		No		--- access days
Non-EU user project:		No		Internal-TA:	No	
				--- industry users		

3.3 3rd Call for Lab Access Proposals (01/06/2021 – 31/08/2021)

This section compiles the proposals received in the 3rd Call for lab access proposals launched from 1st June 2021 to 31st August 2021. For each proposal, the title, user organisation/s, host infrastructure/s and access status are presented.

The following list provides an executive summary of the call outcomes:

- 3 proposals received, all accepted by the USP.
- Type of organisation: 2 from Universities + 1 from Research Organisations.
- Access duration: 12-34 access days, 22 access days (average).
- User Groups from:
 - EU: 1 proposal (Germany).
 - Associated Countries: 1 proposal (Switzerland).
 - Non-EU: 1 proposal (India).

1	PETER	<i>Risk management for electromagnetic interference of smart grid systems, H2020 PETER project</i>				
		User Group Organisations:	Bundeswehr, WIS and Leibniz Universität Hannover		Germany	
		Host Research Installation:	National Smart Grid Laboratory (SINTEF)			
		Access Status:	Completed		2 users	
			Remote Access		34 access days	
		Industry user project:	No			--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No			

2	FLEVOEWIM	<i>A fuzzy logic based efficient and robust control of EVs with open-end winding induction motor drive</i>				
		User Group Organisations:	National Institute of Technology Warangal		India	
		Host Research Installation:	National Smart Grid Laboratory (SINTEF)			
		Access Status:	Completed		2 users	
			Remote Access		20 access days	
		Industry user project:	No			--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No			

3	VEHICLE	<i>Validation of benchmark system for charging control investigation</i>				
		User Group Organisations:	Zurich University of Applied Science Ricerca Sistema Energético (RSE) Canmrt ENERGY, Natural Resources Canada (NRCan) University of Strathclyde		Switzerland Italy Canada UK	
		Host Research Installation:	SYSLAB and Energy Systems Simulation Lab (DTU)			
		Access Status:	Completed		6 users	
			Remote Access		12 access days	
		Industry user project:	No			--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	Yes	2 access days		

3.4 4th Call for Lab Access Proposals (01/10/2021 – 31/12/2021)

This section compiles the proposals received in the 4th Call for lab access proposals launched from 1st October 2021 to 31st December 2021. For each proposal, the title, user organisation/s, host infrastructure/s and access status are presented.

The following list provides an executive summary of the call outcomes:

- 16 proposals received, 3 not accepted by the USP, 3 withdrawn by the user, 2 unfeasible.
- Type of organisation: 2 from Industry + 12 from Universities + 2 from other organisations.
- Access duration: 5-34 access days, 19 access days (average).
- User Groups from:
 - EU: 4 proposals (Cyprus/Austria, Italy, Czech Republic).

- Associated Countries: 2 proposals (Turkey, Switzerland).
- Non-EU: 10 proposals (USA, India, South Africa, Brazil, Pakistan).

1	PMUs-Cloud	Method for rotational inertia metering and forecasting using cloud synchrophasors data				
		User Group Organisations:	Splight Artificial Energy		Chile	
		Host Research Installation:	Electrical Sustainable Power Lab (TU Delft)			
		Access Status:	Withdrawn by user		--- users	
					--- access days	
		Remote Access		--- access days		
		Industry user project:	Yes	Splight Artificial Energy <i>www.splight-ae.com</i>		--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No			
2	VOLTME-TER	Voltage Regulation Monitoring in Distribution Network Integrated with PV and degraded Battery				
		User Group Organisations:	Motilal Nehru National Institute of Technology Allahabad		India	
		Host Research Installation:	---			
		Access Status:	Not approved by USP		--- users	
					--- access days	
		Remote Access		--- access days		
		Industry user project:	No			--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No			
3	DynOMO	Dynamic Interaction of Offshore Wind Farm Through MTDC Network with Onshore AC Grid				
		User Group Organisations:	IIT Kanpur Østfold University College		India Norway	
		Host Research Installation:	Electrical Sustainable Power Lab (TU Delft)			
		Access Status:	Withdrawn by user		--- users	
					--- access days	
		Remote Access		--- access days		
		Industry user project:	No			--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No			
4	AIDGRIDS	Artificial Intelligent Digitalized Solutions for Smart Grids				
		User Group Organisations:	University of Cyprus - FOSS Research Centre for Sustainable Energy Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT)		Cyprus Austria	
		Host Research Installation:	Smart Electricity Systems and Technologies Laboratory (AIT) Low Voltage Experimental Microgrid Lab (FOSS-UCY)			
		Access Status:	Completed		5 users	
					18 access days	
		Remote Access		--- access days		
		Industry user project:	No			--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	Yes	18 access days		

5	CybTEST	Cyber attack in PV system for voltage regulation in distribution network				
		User Group Organisations:	Motilal Nehru National Institute of Technology Alahabad Østfold University College		India Norway	
		Host Research Installation:	Intelligent Energy Testbed (VTT)			
		Access Status:	Completed		3 users	
					20 access days	
				Remote Access	--- access days	
		Industry user project:	No			--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No			
6	LD-RTCosim	Locally Distributed Real-time Co-simulation Infrastructure for Scalable System Simulation				
		User Group Organisations:	Politecnico di Torino		Italy	
		Host Research Installation:	Real-Time Lab (RWTH Aachen University)			
		Access Status:	Completed		1 user	
					20 access days	
				Remote Access	--- access days	
		Industry user project:	No			--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No			
7	SMPS	Smart Microgrid Protection System				
		User Group Organisations:	Indian Institute of Technology Guwahati		India	
		Host Research Installation:	Smart Electricity Systems and Technologies Laboratory (AIT)			
		Access Status:	Completed		3 users	
					22 access days	
				Remote Access	--- access days	
		Industry user project:	No			--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No			
8	AGIPDem	Advanced GPT Inverter Physical Demonstration				
		User Group Organisations:	University of Cape Town		South Africa	
		Host Research Installation:	Dynamic Power Systems Laboratory (UST) Power Networks Demonstration Centre (UST)			
		Access Status:	Completed		2 users	
					21 access days	
				Remote Access	--- access days	
		Industry user project:	No			--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No			
9	HCEQIS	Hosting Capacity and Energy Quality in Isolated Systems				
		User Group Organisations:	eAmazônia – Energia Sustentável e Inovação		Brazil	
		Host Research Installation:	---			
		Access Status:	Not approved by USP		--- users	
					--- access days	
		Remote Access	--- access days			
Industry user project:	No			--- industry users		

10	RCPIso	Radio communication as a perpetuity tool for isolated photovoltaic systems				
		User Group Organisations:		Centro de Pesquisas de Energia Eletrica (CEPEL), ELECTROBRAS		Brazil
		Host Research Installation:		---		
		Access Status:		Unfeasible		--- users
				Remote Access		--- access days
		Industry user project:		Yes	CEPEL, ELECTROBRAS www.cepel.br	
Non-EU user project:		Yes	Internal-TA:	No		
11	IoRE	Internet of Renewable Energy (IoRE): Application of IoT/IoE Intelligent Information and Communication System for Purely Renewable Island and Bulk Electricity Networks				
		User Group Organisations:		University of Pardubice		Czech Republic
		Host Research Installation:		---		
		Access Status:		Not approved by USP		--- users
				Remote Access		--- access days
		Industry user project:		No		
Non-EU user project:		No	Internal-TA:	No		
12	IC2PSofMG	Intelligent Control to Enhance Power Smoothing of DERs based Microgrid				
		User Group Organisations:		Dicle University		Turkey
		Host Research Installation:		Distributed Generation Laboratory (CRES)		
		Access Status:		Completed		1 user
				Remote Access		15 access days
		Industry user project:		No		
Non-EU user project:		No	Internal-TA:	No		
13	SEFL EMTR	Single-end fault locator based on the electromagnetic time reversal theory				
		User Group Organisations:		Streamer Electric AG		Switzerland
		Host Research Installation:		Power Networks Demonstration Centre (UST) Demonstration & Experimentation Unit (OCT)		
		Access Status:		Withdrawn by user		--- users
				Remote Access		--- access days
		Industry user project:		Yes	Streamer Electric AG www.streamer-electric.com	
Non-EU user project:		No	Internal-TA:	No		
14	TRMDRO	Torque Ripple Minimization for DTC of PMSM Drive Using Duty Ratio Optimization				
		User Group Organisations:		National Institute of Technology Warangal		India
		Host Research Installation:		---		
		Access Status:		Unfeasible		--- users
				Remote Access		--- access days
		Industry user project:		No		
Non-EU user project:		Yes	Internal-TA:	No		

15	CYPRESS	Cyber-Physical Resilient Distribution System			
		User Group Organisations:	Lahore University of Management Sciences		Pakistan
		Host Research Installation:	Smart Electricity Systems and Technologies Laboratory (AIT)		
		Access Status:	Completed		2 users
					34 access days
				Remote Access	17 access days
		Industry user project:	No	---	
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No		

16	RE-LENDER	Reinforcement Learning and Nonlinear MPC algorithm for the Distributed Energy Resources				
		User Group Organisations:	Politecnico di Milano		Italy	
		Host Research Installation:	Smart Grid Interoperability Lab in Petten, NL (JRC, EC)			
		Access Status:	Completed		2 users	
					5 access days	
				Remote Access	---	access days
		Industry user project:	No	---		industry users
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No			

3.5 5th Call for Lab Access Proposals (01/02/2022 – 30/04/2022)

This section compiles the proposals received in the 5th Call for lab access proposals launched from 1st February 2022 to 30th April 2022. For each proposal, the title, user organisation/s, host infrastructure/s and access status are presented.

The following list provides an executive summary of the call outcomes:

- 11 proposals received, all accepted by the USP, 1 withdrawn by the user.
- Type of organisation: 1 from Industry + 9 from Universities + 1 from other organisations.
- Access duration: 8-27 access days, 15 access days (average).
- User Groups from:
 - EU: 3 proposals (France, Spain, Greece).
 - Associated Countries: 3 proposals (Turkey, Serbia).
 - Non-EU: 5 proposals (Brazil, India, Egypt, Jordan).

1	Grid Ex-panDER	A cost-effective solution for the non-firm grid connection of Low Voltage Generators			
		User Group Organisations:	Roseau Technologies		France
		Host Research Installation:	Test Center for Smart Grids and Electromobility (IEE)		
		Access Status:	Completed		2 users
					15 access days
				Remote Access	3 access days
		Industry user project:	Yes	Roseau Technologies <i>roseautechnologies.com</i>	
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No		

2	CPHILT-GFVSC	Control and Power Hardware-in-the-Loop Testing of Grid-Forming Voltage Source Converters				
		User Group Organisations:		Universidad de Sevilla		Spain
		Host Research Installation:		Electric Energy Systems Laboratory (ICCS-NTUA)		
		Access Status:		Completed		2 users
						27 access days
				Remote Access		--- access days
		Industry user project:	No			
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No			

3	PHIL-Rep	Ensuring Replicability of Power HIL Simulations: A Proposal towards a Standards Tests				
		User Group Organisations:		Centro de Pesquisas de Energia Eletrica (CEPEL), ELECTROBRAS		Brazil
		Host Research Installation:		Electrical Sustainable Power Lab (TU Delft)		
		Access Status:		Completed		1 user
						20 access days
				Remote Access		--- access days
		Industry user project:	Yes	CEPEL, ELECTROBRAS www.cepel.br		1 industry user
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No			

4	EMS4GCHS	Energy Management System for Grid Connected PV-Battery-Diesel Hybrid System				
		User Group Organisations:		Dicle University University of Kurdistan		Turkey Iran
		Host Research Installation:		SESA-Lab (OFFIS)		
		Access Status:		Completed		2 users
						15 access days
				Remote Access		--- access days
		Industry user project:	No			
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No			

5	HIHREMS	Hybridized Intelligent Home Renewable Energy Management System				
		User Group Organisations:		Dicle University University of Belgrade		Turkey Serbia
		Host Research Installation:		Smart Grid Interoperability Lab in Ispra, IT (JRC, EC)		
		Access Status:		Withdrawn by user		--- users
						--- access days
		Remote Access		--- access days		
Industry user project:	No				--- industry users	

6	ProMiSe	Assessing the Provision of a Multi-Ancillary Service Framework provided by PV-BES Systems				
		User Group Organisations:		Democritus University of Thrace Aristotle University of Thessaloniki		Greece
		Host Research Installation:		Dynamic Power Systems Laboratory (UST)		
		Access Status:		Completed		3 users
						10 access days
				Remote Access		5 access days
Industry user project:	No				--- industry users	
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No			

7	PERFECT	<i>PERformance Analysis of PV Integrated Distribution Network with combination of DiffERent Control Strategies and Communication NeTwork</i>				
		User Group Organisations:	Motilal Nehru National Institute of Technology Alahabad			India
		Host Research Installation:	Intelligent Energy Testbed (VTT)			
		Access Status:	Completed			1 user
						20 access days
		Remote Access			--- access days	
		Industry user project:	No	---		
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No			
8	CyDER-FORT	<i>Fortified Cyber Defense in DER Management Systems</i>				
		User Group Organisations:	Marmara University			Turkey
		Host Research Installation:	Smart Grid Technologies Lab (TECNALIA)			
		Access Status:	Completed			1 user
						10 access days
		Remote Access			--- access days	
		Industry user project:	No	---		
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No			
9	IETGPSC	<i>Investigating the Effect of Third Generation Photovoltaics (Large Scale Perovskite Solar Cells) Penetration in Electric Grid</i>				
		User Group Organisations:	Kafrelsheikh University-Faculty of Engineering			Egypt
		Host Research Installation:	Electric Energy Systems Laboratory (ICCS-NTUA)			
		Access Status:	Completed			1 user
						10 access days
		Remote Access			--- access days	
		Industry user project:	No	---		
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No			
10	DynaPEM	<i>Dynamic Characterization of Power-Electronics-based-Microgrid</i>				
		User Group Organisations:	Tafila Technical University			Jordan
		Host Research Installation:	Intelligent Energy Testbed (VTT)			
		Access Status:	Completed			3 users
						8 access days
		Remote Access			--- access days	
		Industry user project:	No	---		
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No			
11	Multigrad-con	<i>Grid Interconnection protocols for Largely Dispersed minigrids/microgrids</i>				
		User Group Organisations:	Indian Institute of Technology Bhubaneswar			India
		Host Research Installation:	National Smart Grid Laboratory (SINTEF)			
		Access Status:	Completed			2 users
						13 access days
		Remote Access			--- access days	
		Industry user project:	No	---		
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No			

3.6 6th Call for Lab Access Proposals (01/06/2022 – 31/08/2022)

This section compiles the proposals received in the 6th Call for lab access proposals launched from 1st June 2022 to 31st August 2022. For each proposal, the title, user organisation/s, host infrastructure/s and access status are presented.

The following list provides an executive summary of the call outcomes:

- 6 proposals received, all accepted by the USP, 1 withdrawn by the user, 1 unfeasible.
- Type of organisation: 2 from Industry + 4 from Universities.
- Access duration: 5-85 access days; 29 access days (average).
- User Groups from:
 - EU: 2 proposals (Portugal, Germany).
 - Non-EU: 4 proposals (India, Japan, Iran, Pakistan).

1	TRMDRO	<i>Torque Ripple Minimization for DTC of PMSM Drive Using Duty Ratio Optimization</i>			
		User Group Organisations:	National Institute of Technology, Warangal		India
		Host Research Installation:	---		
		Access Status:	Unfeasible		--- users
			Remote Access		--- access days
		Industry user project:	No		
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No		

2	ISAIPS	<i>Study of innovative impedance-based stability analysis for the power systems composed of inverter-based resources</i>			
		User Group Organisations:	Toyo University		Japan
		Host Research Installation:	National Smart Grid Laboratory (SINTEF)		
		Access Status:	Completed		3 users
			Remote Access		10 access days
		Industry user project:	No		
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No		

3	FaultTS	<i>Fault TroubleShooter</i>			
		User Group Organisations:	ENEIDA.IO		Portugal
		Host Research Installation:	Power Networks Demonstration Centre (UST)		
		Access Status:	Completed		3 users
			Remote Access		5 access days
		Industry user project:	Yes	ENEIDA.IO https://eneida.io/	
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No		

4	Sono LV-MCU	Testing and Validation of LV MPPT Center Unit (MCU)			
		User Group Organisations:	Sono Motors GmbH		Germany
		Host Research Installation:	Distributed Generation Laboratory (GRES)		
		Access Status:	Completed		1 user
			Remote Access		85 access days
		Industry user project:	Yes	Sono Motors GmbH www.sonomotors.com	
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No		

5	CTCPM	Cyber Threats in Cyber-Physical Microgrids			
		User Group Organisations:	University of Kurdistan		Iran
		Host Research Installation:	Intelligent Energy Testbed (VTT)		
		Access Status:	Completed		1 user
			Remote Access		15 access days
		Industry user project:	No		
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No	--- industry users	

6	CYPRESS-Wood	Cyber-Physical Resilient Distribution System with secondary controller design			
		User Group Organisations:	Lahore University of Management Sciences		Pakistan
		Host Research Installation:	Electric Energy Systems Laboratory (ICCS-NTUA)		
		Access Status:	Withdrawn by user		--- users
			Remote Access		--- access days
		Industry user project:	No		
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No		

3.7 7th Call for Lab Access Proposals (01/10/2022 – 31/12/2022)

This section compiles the proposals received in the 7th Call for lab access proposals launched from 1st October 2022 to 31st December 2022. For each proposal, the title, user organisation/s, host infrastructure/s and access status are presented.

The following list provides an executive summary of the call outcomes:

- 25 proposals received, 2 not accepted by the USP, 4 withdrawn by the user, 2 rejected (non-EU limit).
- Type of organisation: 3 from Industry + 21 from Universities + 1 from Research Organisations.
- Access duration: 5-40 access days, 17 access days (average).
- User Groups from:
 - EU: 10 proposals (Finland, Estonia, Czech Republic, Portugal, Italy, Spain, Germany).
 - Associated Countries: 6 proposals (UK, Switzerland, Turkey).

– Non-EU: 9 proposals (India, Colombia).

1	BCF	<i>A Lightweight Private Blockchain-Based Secure Communication Framework For Events Monitoring and Control in the Smart Grid Applications</i>				
		User Group Organisations:	University of Vaasa		Finland	
		Host Research Installation:	---			
		Access Status:	Unfeasible		--- users	
					--- access days	
		Remote Access		--- access days		
		Industry user project:	No			--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No			
2	PROTECT	<i>Impacts of PV Generations on the Performance of Positive Sequence Memory Polarized Distance Relays</i>				
		User Group Organisations:	Indian Institute of Science		India	
		Host Research Installation:	Electrical Sustainable Power Lab (TU Delft)			
		Access Status:	Completed		1 user	
					24 access days	
		Remote Access		--- access days		
Industry user project:	No			--- industry users		
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No			
3	ITCMPD	<i>Instrument transformer condition monitoring using partial discharges</i>				
		User Group Organisations:	Tallinn University of Technology		Estonia	
		Host Research Installation:	Demonstration & Experimentation Unit (OCT)			
		Access Status:	Completed		1 user	
					24 access days	
		Remote Access		18 access days		
Industry user project:	No			--- industry users		
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No			
4	TRMDRO	<i>Torque Ripple Minimization for DTC of PMSM Drive Using Duty Ratio Optimization</i>				
		User Group Organisations:	National Institute of Technology, Warangal		India	
		Host Research Installation:	---			
		Access Status:	Not accepted (non-EU limit)		--- users	
					--- access days	
		Remote Access		--- access days		
Industry user project:	No			--- industry users		
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No			

5	ColdHarmonics	Harmonics Measurement of fast DC EV Charging of under low temperatures					
		User Group Organisations:	University of Strathclyde		UK		
		Host Research Installation:	SYSLAB and Energy Systems Simulation Lab (DTU)				
		Access Status:	Completed			5 users	
						10 access days	
		Remote Access			--- access days		
		Industry user project:	No				--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	Yes	10 access days			

6	IsMAER	Isolated Microgrids for Aggregated Energy Resources					
		User Group Organisations:	Czech Technical University in Prague (CTU-P)		Czech Republic		
		Host Research Installation:	Distributed Energy Resources Test Facility (RSE)				
		Access Status:	Withdrawn by user			--- users	
						--- access days	
		Remote Access			--- access days		
		Industry user project:	No				--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No				

7	E2MPC	Model Predictive Control with Stability Guarantee for PWM-VSC and PWM-CSC with Electrical Energy Storage					
		User Group Organisations:	Universidad Tecnológica de Pereira		Colombia		
		Host Research Installation:	National Smart Grid Laboratory (SINTEF)				
		Access Status:	Completed			1 user	
						23 access days	
		Remote Access			--- access days		
		Industry user project:	No				--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No				

8	EMPC-DC	Economic Model Predictive Control for DC Microgrids					
		User Group Organisations:	Universidad Tecnológica de Pereira		Colombia		
		Host Research Installation:	Smart Grid Technologies Lab (TECNALIA)				
		Access Status:	Completed			1 user	
						40 access days	
		Remote Access			--- access days		
		Industry user project:	No				--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No				

9	HVLD	High Voltage Line Down					
		User Group Organisations:	ENEIDA.IO		Portugal		
		Host Research Installation:	Power Networks Demonstration Centre (UST)				
		Access Status:	Completed			3 users	
						5 access days	
		Remote Access			--- access days		
		Industry user project:	Yes	ENEIDA.IO https://eneida.io/			3 industry users
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No				

10	EnergyCom	Energy Community Optimization					
		User Group Organisations:	University of Genova		Italy		
		Host Research Installation:	---				
		Access Status:	Not approved by USP			--- users	
			Remote Access			--- access days	
		Industry user project:	No				--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No				

11	POEM	Protection and Optimization for Efficient Microgrids					
		User Group Organisations:	ABB Corporate Research Center Germany ABB Corporate Research Center USA ABB SpA, Smart Power division, Italy		Germany USA Italy		
		Host Research Installation:	Distributed Energy Resources Test Facility (RSE)				
		Access Status:	Completed			3 users	
			Remote Access			--- access days	
		Industry user project:	Yes	ABB Germany https://new.abb.com/de/ueber-uns/abb-forschungszentrum ABB USA https://global.abb/group/en/technology/corporate-researchcenters/usa		3 industry users	
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No				

12	CO-FLEX	Coordinating residential flexibility resources in a socio-technical co-simulation design					
		User Group Organisations:	École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL)		Switzerland		
		Host Research Installation:	SESA-Lab (OFFIS)				
		Access Status:	Completed			1 user	
			Remote Access			9 access days	
		Industry user project:	No				--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No				

13	MOTIVATION-ERA	MModel Identification for VoltAge Improvement in DistribuTION Network- Energy Resources EquivAlence					
		User Group Organisations:	Motilal Nehru National Institute of Technology Allahabad Østfold University College		India Norway		
		Host Research Installation:	Distributed Energy Resources Test Facility (RSE)				
		Access Status:	Completed			3 users	
			Remote Access			10 access days	
		Industry user project:	No				--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No				

14	MOTIVATION- ISLE	<i>MModel Identification for VoltAge Improvement in DistribuTION Network- Integrated Energy ReSources EquivaLEnce</i>					
		User Group Organisations:		Motilal Nehru National Institute of Technology Allahabad Østfold University College		India Norway	
		Host Research Installation:		Distributed Energy Resources Test Facility (RSE)			
		Access Status:		Completed		3 users	
						10 access days	
				Remote Access		--- access days	
		Industry user project:	No				--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No				
15	ABILITY	<i>Analysing cyber attacks in control loop for power oscillatory stability</i>					
		User Group Organisations:		Motilal Nehru National Institute of Technology Allahabad Østfold University College		India Norway	
		Host Research Installation:		Electrical Sustainable Power Lab (TU Delft)			
		Access Status:		Completed		3 users	
						20 access days	
				Remote Access		--- access days	
		Industry user project:	No				--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No				
16	PVIPSFS	<i>PV Integrated Power System Frequency Restoration under Solar Irradiance Variation</i>					
		User Group Organisations:		Dicle University Dicle DSO		Turkey	
		Host Research Installation:		---			
		Access Status:		Not approved by USP		--- users	
						--- access days	
				Remote Access		--- access days	
		Industry user project:	Yes				--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No				
17	ESS-IMG2C-PVoF	<i>Energy Storage System Integrated Microgrid Control Considering PV output Forecasting</i>					
		User Group Organisations:		Firat University Dicle University Dicle DSO		Turkey	
		Host Research Installation:		Smart Grid Interoperability Lab in Ispra, IT (JRC, EC)			
		Access Status:		Withdrawn by user		--- users	
						--- access days	
				Remote Access		--- access days	
		Industry user project:	Yes				--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No				

18	GGWO-TSKFS-CoG-CHRESB	<i>GGWO-TSK-FS-Based Control of a Grid-Connected Hybrid System Integrating Renewable Energies and Batteries</i>				
		User Group Organisations:		Inonu University Dicle University Dicle DSO		Turkey
		Host Research Installation:		Electric Energy Systems Laboratory (ICCS-NTUA)		
		Access Status:		Withdrawn by user		--- users
				Remote Access		--- access days
		Industry user project:	Yes			
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No			

19	HFMP4STVSI	<i>Hybrid Fuzzy Model Predictive Control for Smooth Transition of Voltage Source Inverters under Harmonics and Unbalances</i>				
		User Group Organisations:		Dicle University		Turkey
		Host Research Installation:		SESA-Lab (OFFIS)		
		Access Status:		Completed		1 user
				Remote Access		19 access days
		Industry user project:	No			
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No			
				--- industry users		

20	MOFOM PV	<i>MOntoring of Failures for Operation and Maintenance PV</i>				
		User Group Organisations:		TECNALIA		Spain
		Host Research Installation:		Distributed Energy Resources Test Facility (RSE)		
		Access Status:		Completed		2 users
				Remote Access		10 access days
		Industry user project:	No			
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	Yes	10 access days		
				--- industry users		

21	MOVES	<i>Model Validation of Sector-coupled Energy Systems – Heat & E-Mobility Use cases</i>				
		User Group Organisations:		Hamburg University of Technology		Germany
		Host Research Installation:		SYSLAB and Energy Systems Simulation Lab (DTU)		
		Access Status:		Completed		3 users
				Remote Access		9 access days
		Industry user project:	No			
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No			
				--- industry users		

22	IES-MG	<i>Experimental method to determine the interoperability, scalability, and security of a defined MG</i>				
		User Group Organisations:		Universidad Nacional de Colombia		Colombia
		Host Research Installation:		---		
		Access Status:		Not accepted (non-EU limit)		--- users
				Remote Access		--- access days
		Industry user project:	No			
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No			
				--- industry users		

23	PLANREC	Planning Renewable Energy Communities (REC): the perspective of Municipalities and Small and Medium Enterprises (SME)			
		User Group Organisations:	Fabbrica Digitale		Italy
		Host Research Installation:	Smart Grid Interoperability Lab in Ispra, IT (JRC, EC)		
		Access Status:	Completed		1 user
					7 access days
			Remote Access	--- access days	
Industry user project:	Yes	fabbricadigitale S.r.l. www.fabbricadigitale.com		1 industry user	
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No		

24	Ener- gética2030	Transformation strategy for the Colombian energy sector in 2030 horizon			
		User Group Organisations:	Universidad Nacional de Colombia		Colombia
		Host Research Installation:	Real-Time Lab (RWTH Aachen University)		
		Access Status:	Withdrawn by user		--- users
					--- access days
			Remote Access	--- access days	
Industry user project:	No			--- industry users	
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No		

25	PHIL- 1phGFVSC	Power Hardware-in-the-Loop Testing of Single-Phase Grid-Forming VSCs in Grid-Connected Mode			
		User Group Organisations:	University of Sevilla		Spain
		Host Research Installation:	Electric Energy Systems Laboratory (ICCS-NTUA)		
		Access Status:	Completed		1 user
					15 access days
			Remote Access	--- access days	
Industry user project:	No			--- industry users	
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No		

3.8 8th Call for Lab Access Proposals (01/02/2023 – 30/04/2023)

This section compiles the proposals received in the 8th Call for lab access proposals launched from 1st February 2023 to 30th April 2023. For each proposal, the title, user organisation/s, host infrastructure/s and access status are presented.

The following list provides an executive summary of the call outcomes:

- 16 proposals received, 1 not accepted by the USP, 6 rejected (non-EU limit).
- Type of organisation: 1 from Industry + 15 from Universities.
- Access duration: 5-27 access days, 12 access days (average).
- User Groups from:
 - EU: 8 proposals (Finland, Greece, Poland, Spain, Denmark, Germany).
 - Associated Countries: 1 proposal (Norway).
 - Non-EU: 7 proposals (Japan, India, Iran, Pakistan).

1	BCF	<i>A Lightweight Private Blockchain-Based Secure Communication Framework For Events Monitoring and Control in the Smart Grid Applications</i>				
		User Group Organisations:		University of Vaasa		Finland
		Host Research Installation:		Electric Energy Systems Laboratory (ICCS-NTUA)		
		Access Status:		Completed		1 user
						19 access days
				Remote Access		--- access days
Industry user project:		No		--- industry users		
Non-EU user project:		No		Internal-TA: No		

2	iniTiate	<i>Developing Digitally Twin Distribution Network Equivalent Models</i>				
		User Group Organisations:		Democritus University of Thrace Aristotle University of Thessaloniki		Greece
		Host Research Installation:		Dynamic Power Systems Laboratory (UST)		
		Access Status:		Completed		3 users
						10 access days
				Remote Access		5 access days
Industry user project:		No		--- industry users		
Non-EU user project:		No		Internal-TA: No		

3	IMSPS	<i>Establishment of impedance-based metrics for stable operation of power systems</i>				
		User Group Organisations:		Toyo University Fukushima Renewable Energy Institute, AIST (FREA) Toshiba Infrastructure Systems & Solutions Corporation		Japan
		Host Research Installation:		---		
		Access Status:		Not accepted (non-EU limit)		--- users
						--- access days
				Remote Access		--- access days
Industry user project:		Yes		--- industry users		
Non-EU user project:		Yes		Internal-TA: No		

4	WindGrid	<i>Wind power plants in dynamic states of the power grid</i>				
		User Group Organisations:		AGH University of Science and Technology		Poland
		Host Research Installation:		Dynamic Power Systems Laboratory (UST)		
		Access Status:		Completed		3 users
						9 access days
				Remote Access		--- access days
Industry user project:		No		--- industry users		
Non-EU user project:		No		Internal-TA: No		

5	AID4EPES	Advanced validation of AI-based anomaly and intrusion Detection for high impact threats in Electrical Power and Energy Systems				
		User Group Organisations:		Atos IT Solutions and Services Iberia		Spain
		Host Research Installation:		National Smart Grid Laboratory (SINTEF)		
		Access Status:		Completed		2 users
				Remote Access		5 access days
		Industry user project:		Yes	ATOS IT Solutions and Services SL https://atos.net/es/spain	
Non-EU user project:		No	Internal-TA:	No		

6	VISION	Voltage stability for grid of nano gridS having variability of photovoltaic generation				
		User Group Organisations:		Motilal Nehru National Institute of Technology Allahabad Østfold University College		India Norway
		Host Research Installation:		---		
		Access Status:		Not accepted (non-EU limit)		--- users
				Remote Access		--- access days
		Industry user project:		No		
Non-EU user project:		Yes	Internal-TA:	No		

7	DEFENSE	High Impedance Arching Fault DEtection For RENewable Penetrated DiStribution Network				
		User Group Organisations:		National Institute of Technology Raipur Østfold University College, Norway		India Norway
		Host Research Installation:		---		
		Access Status:		Not accepted (non-EU limit)		--- users
				Remote Access		--- access days
		Industry user project:		No		
Non-EU user project:		Yes	Internal-TA:	No		

8	TwinNET	Developing grey-box digital TWInS for active distribution NETWORK analysis				
		User Group Organisations:		Aristotle University of Thessaloniki Democritus University of Thrace		Greece
		Host Research Installation:		SYSLAB and Energy Systems Simulation Lab (DTU)		
		Access Status:		Completed		3 users
				Remote Access		10 access days
		Industry user project:		No		
Non-EU user project:		No	Internal-TA:	No	--- industry users	

9	DDPAOP	Data-Driven Predictive Approach for Out-of-Step Protection in Modern Power Systems				
		User Group Organisations:	Smart/Micro Grids Research Center, University of Kurdistan			Iran
		Host Research Installation:	---			
		Access Status:	Not accepted (non-EU limit)			--- users
			Remote Access			--- access days
		Industry user project:	No			
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No			

10	DRLeMPC4-RVFSinMG	Deep Reinforcement Learning-Enhanced Model Predictive Control for Robust Voltage and Frequency Stabilization in Microgrids with Uncertainties				
		User Group Organisations:	Institute of Southern Punjab Dicle University			Pakistan Turkey
		Host Research Installation:	---			
		Access Status:	Not accepted (non-EU limit)			--- users
			Remote Access			--- access days
		Industry user project:	No			
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No			

11	M4Grid	Metrology for Smart Electrical Grids				
		User Group Organisations:	AGH University of Krakow			Poland
		Host Research Installation:	Flex Power Grid Laboratory (KEMA Labs)			
		Access Status:	Completed			3 users
			Remote Access			10 access days
		Industry user project:	No			
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No			

12	RTT-Flow	Real time testing of copper-based redox flow batteries performance for frequency regulation service in power grids				
		User Group Organisations:	Aarhus University			Denmark
		Host Research Installation:	Smart Electricity Systems and Technologies Laboratory (AIT)			
		Access Status:	Completed			2 users
			Remote Access			27 access days
		Industry user project:	No			
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No			

13	DTCPMS-MDRA	DTC of PMSM based on a Simple Duty Ratio Approach with Torque Ripple Reduction				
		User Group Organisations:	National Institute of Technology, Warangal			India
		Host Research Installation:	---			
		Access Status:	Not approved by USP			--- users
			Remote Access			--- access days
		Industry user project:	No			
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No			

14	DISeCTER	<i>Distributed Security Cyber Testbed for Energy Research</i>			
		User Group Organisations:	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)		Germany
		Host Research Installation:	SYSLAB and Energy Systems Simulation Lab (DTU)		
		Access Status:	Completed		2 users
					10 access days
		Remote Access		--- access days	
Industry user project:	No			--- industry users	
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No		

15	FOSTER	<i>Framework for service restoration of cyber-physical distribution systems with high penetration of distributed energy resources</i>			
		User Group Organisations:	Lahore University of Management Sciences		Pakistan
		Host Research Installation:	---		
		Access Status:	Not accepted (non-EU limit)		--- users
					--- access days
		Remote Access		--- access days	
Industry user project:	No			--- industry users	
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No		

16	CGNN4Grid	<i>Causal Graph Neural Network method for Enhanced Parameter Forecasting in Power Distribution Networks</i>			
		User Group Organisations:	Western Norway University of Applied Sciences		Norway
		Host Research Installation:	Smart Electricity Systems and Technologies Laboratory (AIT)		
		Access Status:	Completed		6 users
					2 access days
		Remote Access		--- access days	
Industry user project:	No			--- industry users	
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No		

3.9 9th Call for Lab Access Proposals (01/06/2023 – 31/08/2023)

This section compiles the proposals received in the 9th Call for lab access proposals launched from 1st June 2023 to 31st August 2023. For each proposal, the title, user organisation/s, host infrastructure/s and access status are presented.

The following list provides an executive summary of the call outcomes:

- 5 proposals received, 1 not accepted by the USP.
- Type of organisation: 3 from Universities + 2 from Research Organisations.
- Access duration: 11-30 access days, 20 access days (average).
- User Groups from:
 - EU: 4 proposals (Germany, Spain, Sweden, Lithuania).
 - Associated Countries: 1 proposal (UK).

1	IaaS Plat- form	Unified Infrastructure-as-a-Service Platform for Distributed Co-simulation of Networked Microgrids					
		User Group Organisations:	German Aerospace Center (DLR), Institute of Networked Energy Systems			Germany	
		Host Research Installation:	IntelligentEnergy Testbed (VTT)				
		Access Status:	Completed			5 users	
			Remote Access			20 access days	
		Industry user project:	No	---			--- access days
		Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No	---	

2	RTPIM	Real-Time Parameter Identification in Microgrids					
		User Group Organisations:	University of Almeria			Spain	
		Host Research Installation:	National Smart Grid Laboratory (SINTEF)				
		Access Status:	Completed			2 users	
			Remote Access			11 access days	
		Industry user project:	No	---			--- access days
		Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No	---	

3	EVEREST	Electric Vehicles and Renewable generation Enabling STable islands in power distribution networks					
		User Group Organisations:	University of Bath			UK	
		Host Research Installation:	Test Center for Smart Grids and Electromobility (IEE)				
		Access Status:	Completed			1 user	
			Remote Access			18 access days	
		Industry user project:	No	---			4 access days
		Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No	---	

4	RCPIN	Resilient Control of Power Inverter Network					
		User Group Organisations:	KTH Royal Institute of Technology			Sweden	
		Host Research Installation:	Smart Electricity Systems and Technologies Laboratory (AIT)				
		Access Status:	Completed			3 users	
			Remote Access			30 access days	
		Industry user project:	No	---			15 access days
		Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No	---	

5	HYPO	Simulation of Industrial Hybrid Power System with Hydrogen					
		User Group Organisations:	Lithuanian Energy Institute			Lithuania	
		Host Research Installation:	---				
		Access Status:	Not approved by USP			---	
			Remote Access			---	
		Industry user project:	No	---			---
		Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No	---	

3.10 10th Call for Lab Access Proposals (01/10/2023 – 31/12/2023)

This section compiles the proposals received in the 10th Call for lab access proposals launched from 1st October 2023 to 31st December 2023. For each proposal, the title, user organisation/s, host infra-structure/s and access status are presented.

The following list provides an executive summary of the call outcomes:

- 16 proposals received, all accepted by the USP, 1 rejected (non-EU limit).
- Type of organisation: 4 from Industry + 10 from Universities + 2 from Research Organisations.
- Access duration: 4-24 access days; 14 access days (average).
- User Groups from:
 - EU: 11 proposals (Belgium, Croatia, Italy, Germany, Portugal, Spain, Malta).
 - Associated Countries: 4 proposals (Switzerland, Turkey, UK).
 - Non-EU: 1 proposal (Australia).

1	EAR-LYFAULT-MONITORING	<i>Early detection and location of severe insulation defects and insulation faults in distribution grids through monitoring using GPS synchronized sensors</i>					
		User Group Organisations:	Ampacimon SA		Belgium		
		Host Research Installation:	Demonstration & Experimentation Unit (OCT)				
		Access Status:	Completed			2 users	
						21 access days	
		Remote Access			18 access days		
		Industry user project:	Yes	AMPACIMON <i>www.ampacimon.com</i>		2 industry users	
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No				

2	EXPLORE-MP3S	<i>Experimental Exploration of Model Predictive Control for 3-Phase Split-Source Inverters</i>					
		User Group Organisations:	UNIVERSITY OF SPLIT - FESB		Croatia		
		Host Research Installation:	Smart Electricity Systems and Technologies Laboratory (AIT)				
		Access Status:	Completed			3 users	
						24 access days	
		Remote Access			--- access days		
		Industry user project:	No			--- industry users	
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No				

3	PHIL-SOFC	<i>Power Hardware In the Loop Study of Novel Integral Reinforcement Learning Based Control Method for Solid Oxide Fuel Cell in DC Microgrid</i>					
		User Group Organisations:	University of Western Australia		Australia		
		Host Research Installation:	---				
		Access Status:	Not accepted (non-EU limit)			--- users	
						--- access days	
		Remote Access			--- access days		
		Industry user project:	No			--- industry users	
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No				

4	RESIDE	Revamping Energy Storage Including Degradation Effects					
		User Group Organisations:	University of Trento		Italy		
		Host Research Installation:	Smart Grid Interoperability Lab in Ispra, IT (JRC, EC)				
		Access Status:	Completed			2 users	
						20 access days	
		Remote Access			--- access days		
Industry user project:	No				--- industry users		
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No				
5	RECDT	Renewable Energy Communities Digital Twin					
		User Group Organisations:	fabbricadigitale S.r.l.		Italy		
		Host Research Installation:	Smart Grid Interoperability Lab in Ispra, IT (JRC, EC)				
		Access Status:	Completed			2 users	
						7 access days	
		Remote Access			--- access days		
Industry user project:	Yes	fabbricadigitale S.r.l. www.fabbricadigitale.com		2 industry users			
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No				
6	DevA-PHIL	Development of new approaches for improved stability and robustness of PHIL simulations					
		User Group Organisations:	European Commission - Joint Research Centre		Italy		
		Host Research Installation:	Distributed Energy Resources Test Facility (RSE)				
		Access Status:	Completed			2 users	
						10 access days	
		Remote Access			--- access days		
Industry user project:	No				--- industry users		
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	Yes	10 access days			
7	DRE4BalanceReserve	Tele control of pooled DRE systems for grid balance reserve applications					
		User Group Organisations:	Technische Hochschule Ulm		Germany		
		Host Research Installation:	Smart Electricity Systems and Technologies Laboratory (AIT)				
		Access Status:	Completed			5 users	
						11 access days	
		Remote Access			--- access days		
Industry user project:	No				--- industry users		
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No				
8	EDyMCE-Nord	Expansion of the initial Dynamic Model of CE with the Nordic power system and implementation on OPAL-RT's ePHASORSim					
		User Group Organisations:	ZHAW Zurich University of Applied Sciences		Switzerland		
		Host Research Installation:	National Smart Grid Laboratory (SINTEF)				
		Access Status:	Completed			2 users	
						7 access days	
		Remote Access			--- access days		
Industry user project:	No				--- industry users		
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No				

9	RECORD	Renewable Energy Communities Optimal Resources Dispatch					
		User Group Organisations:	Ricerca sul Sistema Energetico, RSE		Italy		
		Host Research Installation:	Smart Grid Interoperability Lab in Ispra, IT (JRC, EC)				
		Access Status:	Completed			3 users	
						10 access days	
		Remote Access			--- access days		
Industry user project:	No				--- industry users		
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	Yes	10 access days			
10	OS-DGApp	Open source supervisory control system platform for distribution grid applications					
		User Group Organisations:	Dicle University		Turkey		
		Host Research Installation:	Distributed Generation Laboratory (CRES)				
		Access Status:	Completed			1 user	
						14 access days	
		Remote Access			10 access days		
Industry user project:	No				--- industry users		
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No				
11	BN	Broken Neutral					
		User Group Organisations:	ENEIDA.IO		Portugal		
		Host Research Installation:	Power Networks Demonstration Centre (UST)				
		Access Status:	Completed			3 users	
						5 access days	
		Remote Access			--- access days		
Industry user project:	Yes	ENEIDA.IO https://eneida.io/		3 industry users			
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No				
12	DI-APROCON	Ground Fault Diagnosis and Protection of Modular Multilevel Converters					
		User Group Organisations:	University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU)		Spain		
		Host Research Installation:	National Smart Grid Laboratory (SINTEF)				
		Access Status:	Completed			3 users	
						6 access days	
		Remote Access			--- access days		
Industry user project:	No				--- industry users		
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No				
13	FLUCCOM	5G-Based Fault Localization in Medium Voltage Underground Cables					
		User Group Organisations:	KU Leuven		Belgium		
		Host Research Installation:	IntelligentEnergy Testbed (VTT)				
		Access Status:	Completed			2 users	
						23 access days	
		Remote Access			--- access days		
Industry user project:	No				--- industry users		
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No				

14	ORCA	<i>OSINT- and AI-based Cybersecurity Resilience Improvement for Electrical Power Distribution Systems</i>				
		User Group Organisations:		Kadir Has University		Turkey
		Host Research Installation:		Distributed Energy Resources Test Facility (RSE)		
		Access Status:		Completed		4 users
						10 access days
				Remote Access		--- access days
Industry user project:		No		--- industry users		
Non-EU user project:		No		Internal-TA: No		

15	DESIRE	<i>Distributed Energy Storage Simulations in Real-Time Environment</i>				
		User Group Organisations:		University of Malta		Malta
		Host Research Installation:		Real-Time Lab (RWTH Aachen University)		
		Access Status:		Completed		2 users
						22 access days
				Remote Access		--- access days
Industry user project:		No		--- industry users		
Non-EU user project:		No		Internal-TA: No		

16	EVGFC	<i>Experimental Assessment and Validation of Damping Impedance Method based Power Hardware-in-the-Loop Interface for Grid Forming Converter Testing</i>				
		User Group Organisations:		WSP UK University of Strathclyde		UK
		Host Research Installation:		Test Center for Smart Grids and Electromobility (IEE)		
		Access Status:		Completed		2 users
						20 access days
				Remote Access		4 access days
Industry user project:		Yes		WSP UK www.wsp.com/en-gb/sectors/power-systems		
Non-EU user project:		No		Internal-TA: Yes 20 access days		

3.11 11th Call for Lab Access Proposals (10/01/2024 – 31/03/2024)

This section compiles the proposals received in the 11th Call for lab access proposals launched from 10th January 2024 to 31st March 2024. For each proposal, the title, user organisation/s, host infrastructure/s and access status are presented.

The following list provides an executive summary of the call outcomes:

- 6 proposals received, all accepted by the USP, 1 withdrawn by the user, 1 rejected (non-EU limit).
- Type of organisation: 6 from Universities.
- Access duration: 10-24 access days; 17 access days (average).
- User Groups from:
 - EU: 3 proposals (Italy, Greece, Romania).
 - Associated Countries: 2 proposals (Turkey).

– Non-EU: 1 proposal (India).

1	HIGH-Z ARCH	<i>Advanced Detection of High Impedance Arching Faults in Renewable Energy-Integrated Distribution Networks</i>					
		User Group Organisations:	National Institute of Technology Raipur Østfold University College			India Norway	
		Host Research Installation:	---				
		Access Status:	Not accepted (non-EU limit)			--- users	
			Remote Access			--- access days	
		Industry user project:	No				--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	Yes	Internal-TA:	No				
2	PIEMgrid	<i>A Passive Grid Impedance Estimation Method Using Existing Harmonics Introduced by Changes in the Load Operating Point</i>					
		User Group Organisations:	Roma Tre University			Italy	
		Host Research Installation:	National Smart Grid Laboratory (SINTEF)				
		Access Status:	Completed			2 users	
			Remote Access			15 access days	
		Industry user project:	No				--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No				
3	DGNet	<i>Developing and validating DiGital twins of Active Distribution NETworks</i>					
		User Group Organisations:	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki			Greece	
		Host Research Installation:	Dynamic Power Systems Laboratory (UST)				
		Access Status:	Completed			1 user	
			Remote Access			10 access days	
		Industry user project:	No				--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No				
4	ACROPOLIS	<i>Enhanced control and exploit flexibility in operation for microgrids using HIL and PHIL experiments</i>					
		User Group Organisations:	National University of Science and Technology Politehnica Bucharest			Romania	
		Host Research Installation:	Electric Energy Systems Laboratory (ICCS-NTUA)				
		Access Status:	Completed			1 user	
			Remote Access			24 access days	
		Industry user project:	No				--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No				

5	ORICSµg	Optimizing Renewable Integration and Control in Smart Microgrids					
		User Group Organisations:	Dicle University Firat University			Turkey	
		Host Research Installation:	Smart Grid Interoperability Lab in Ispra, IT (JRC, EC)				
		Access Status:	Withdrawn by user			--- users	
						--- access days	
		Remote Access			--- access days		
		Industry user project:	No				--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No				

6	DRIMPC-Stability	Integrating Deep Reinforcement Learning and Model Predictive Control for Microgrid Stability					
		User Group Organisations:	Dicle University			Turkey	
		Host Research Installation:	Real-Time Lab (RWTH Aachen University)				
		Access Status:	Completed			1 user	
						20 access days	
		Remote Access			--- access days		
		Industry user project:	No				--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No				

3.12 12th Call for Lab Access Proposals (01/04/2024 – 30/06/2024)

This section compiles the proposals received in the 12th Call for lab access proposals launched from 1st April 2024 to 30th June 2024. For each proposal, the title, user organisation/s, host infrastructure/s and access status are presented.

The following list provides an executive summary of the call outcomes:

- 5 proposals received, all accepted by the USP.
- Type of organisation: 5 from Universities.
- Access duration: 10-25 access days, 15 access days (average).
- User Groups from:
 - EU: 3 proposals (Greece, Italy, The Netherlands).
 - Associated Countries: 2 proposals (UK, Turkey).

1	CAILIM	Cyber-attack investigations on GFL and GFM inverters of a microgrid					
		User Group Organisations:	ICCS-NTUA			Greece	
		Host Research Installation:	Dynamic Power Systems Laboratory (UST)				
		Access Status:	Completed			1 user	
						25 access days	
		Remote Access			11 access days		
		Industry user project:	No				--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	Yes	25 access days			

2	TS-HVDC	<i>Transient stability enhancement of multi-infeed AC offshore islands for large-scale HVDC interconnection and wind integration</i>			
		User Group Organisations:	Manchester Metropolitan University WSP UK BarcelonaTech, UPC		UK UK Spain
		Host Research Installation:	Smart Grid Technologies Lab (TECNALIA)		
		Access Status:	Completed		4 users
			Remote Access		10 access days
		Industry user project:	Yes	WSP UK www.wsp.com/en-gb/sectors/power-systems	
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No		
3	REMOTEC	<i>REinforcement learning for Microgrid Optimization and TEMperature Control</i>			
		User Group Organisations:	Politecnico di Milano - POLIMILI		Italy
		Host Research Installation:	SYSLAB and Energy Systems Simulation Lab (DTU)		
		Access Status:	Completed		3 users
			Remote Access		10 access days
		Industry user project:	No		
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No		
4	SMART-DROOP	<i>Smart Inverter Droop Setting to Solve Voltage Issues in Distribution Networks</i>			
		User Group Organisations:	Abdullah Gul University Kadir Has University Marmara University		Turkey
		Host Research Installation:	Distributed Energy Resources Test Facility (RSE)		
		Access Status:	Completed		3 users
			Remote Access		10 access days
		Industry user project:	No		
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No		
5	HEMSVRT	<i>Home Energy Management System Validation in Real Time</i>			
		User Group Organisations:	Technological University Eindhoven (TU/e)		The Netherlands
		Host Research Installation:	Smart Grid Technologies Lab (TECNALIA)		
		Access Status:	Completed		2 users
			Remote Access		20 access days
		Industry user project:	No		
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No		

3.13 13th Call for Lab Access Proposals (01/07/2024 – 30/09/2024)

This section compiles the proposals received in the 13th Call for lab access proposals launched from 1st July 2024 to 30th September 2024. For each proposal, the title, user organisation/s, host infrastructure/s and access status are presented.

The following list provides an executive summary of the call outcomes:

- 14 proposals received, all accepted by the USP, 1 withdrawn by the user, 1 unfeasible.
- Type of organisation: 2 from Industry + 9 from Universities + 3 from Research Organisations.
- Access duration: 5-21 access days, 13 access days (average).
- User Groups from:
 - EU: 8 proposals (Germany, Spain, Belgium, Greece, Portugal).
 - Associated Countries: 6 proposals (Norway, Turkey, Switzerland).

1	WASIPS	Wide Area System Integrity Protection Schemes for Digitalized Substations					
		User Group Organisations:	OFFIS			Germany	
		Host Research Installation:	Power Networks Demonstration Centre (UST)				
		Access Status:	Completed			2 users	
						15 access days	
		Remote Access			11 access days		
		Industry user project:	No				--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	Yes	15 access days			

2	oZmLib61850	Validation of IEC 61850-9-2 protocol in openZmeter smart meter					
		User Group Organisations:	University of Almeria Zred Comunicaciones y Automatizacion SL			Spain	
		Host Research Installation:	National Smart Grid Laboratory (SINTEF)				
		Access Status:	Completed			3 users	
						21 access days	
		Remote Access			16 access days		
Industry user project:	Yes	Zred Comunicaciones y Automatización www.openzmeter.com			1 industry users		
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No				

3	LIVABLE-LV	Leveraging Model Identification for Voltage Improvement in Renewable-Powered LV Microgrids					
		User Group Organisations:	Østfold University College			Norway	
		Host Research Installation:	Low Voltage Experimental Microgrid Laboratory (UCY)				
		Access Status:	Completed			1 user	
						10 access days	
		Remote Access			--- access days		
Industry user project:	No				--- industry users		
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No				

4	DARC PV	PV arc detection device feasibility test					
		User Group Organisations:	KU Leuven			Belgium	
		Host Research Installation:	Smart Grid Interoperability Lab in Ispra, IT (JRC, EC)				
		Access Status:	Completed			2 users	
						10 access days	
		Remote Access			--- access days		
Industry user project:	No				--- industry users		
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No				

5	RENEWIES	RENewable Energy Integration With Efficiency of Smartgrid					
		User Group Organisations:	Cumhuriyet University		Turkey		
		Host Research Installation:	Smart Electricity Systems and Technologies Laboratory (AIT)				
		Access Status:	Completed			1 user	
						15 access days	
		Remote Access			--- access days		
		Industry user project:	No				--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No				
6	QUINPOR-TION	Uncertainty Propagation in PMU-based Control Decision					
		User Group Organisations:	Swiss Federal Institute of Metrology, METAS		Switzerland		
		Host Research Installation:	Dynamic Power Systems Laboratory (UST)				
		Access Status:	Completed			1 user	
						15 access days	
		Remote Access			3 access days		
		Industry user project:	No				--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No				
7	ForDis	Evaluation of the grid-support functions of Grid Forming control strategies in front of disturbances					
		User Group Organisations:	CITCEA-UPC Universidade Estadual de Campinas (UNICAMP)		Spain Brazil		
		Host Research Installation:	---				
		Access Status:	Unfeasible			--- users	
						--- access days	
		Remote Access			--- access days		
		Industry user project:	No				--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No				
8	5G-SmartPV	5G-Driven Edge Computing for Real-Time Monitoring and Control of Photovoltaic Systems in Smart Grids					
		User Group Organisations:	RWTH AACHEN UNIVERSITÄT		Germany		
		Host Research Installation:	IntelligentEnergy Testbed (VTT)				
		Access Status:	Completed			1 user	
						20 access days	
		Remote Access			--- access days		
		Industry user project:	No				--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	Yes	20 access days			
9	HyMiCO-RPC	Hybrid Microgrid Control Optimization for Reactive Power Compensation					
		User Group Organisations:	Dicle University		Turkey		
		Host Research Installation:	Real-Time Lab (RWTH Aachen University)				
		Access Status:	Completed			1 user	
						15 access days	
		Remote Access			--- access days		
		Industry user project:	No				--- industry users
Non-EU user project:	No	Internal-TA:	No				

10	AESI-HM	Advanced Energy Storage Integration in Hybrid Microgrids for Enhanced Stability				
		User Group Organisations:		Dicle University Dicle DSO		Turkey
		Host Research Installation:		Dynamic Power Systems Laboratory (UST)		
		Access Status:		Withdrawn by user		--- users
				Remote Access		--- access days
		Industry user project:	Yes			
Non-EU user project:		No	Internal-TA:	No		

11	BiFlow-HMG	Bidirectional Power Flow and Inverter Control in AC/DC Hybrid Microgrids				
		User Group Organisations:		Dicle University		Turkey
		Host Research Installation:		Real-Time Lab (RWTH Aachen University)		
		Access Status:		Completed		1 user
				Remote Access		12 access days
		Industry user project:	No			
Non-EU user project:		No	Internal-TA:	No	--- industry users	

12	AID4RISC-V-EPES	AI-based Intrusion Detection for RISC-V Platforms in Electric Power and Energy Systems				
		User Group Organisations:		Atos IT Solutions and Services Iberia		Spain
		Host Research Installation:		National Smart Grid Laboratory (SINTEF)		
		Access Status:		Completed		2 users
				Remote Access		10 access days
		Industry user project:	Yes	ATOS IT Solutions and Services SL https://atos.net/es/spain		3 access days
Non-EU user project:		No	Internal-TA:	No	2 industry users	

13	MCR	Microgrids Cyber Resilience				
		User Group Organisations:		WSP UK ICCS-NTUA		UK Greece
		Host Research Installation:		National Smart Grid Laboratory (SINTEF)		
		Access Status:		Completed		2 users
				Remote Access		5 access days
		Industry user project:	Yes	WSP UK www.wsp.com/en-gb/sectors/power-systems		--- access days
Non-EU user project:		No	Internal-TA:	Yes	1 industry user	
		5 access days				

14	HyStorization	Characterization tests for hybrid storage systems – Li-ion and Vanadium Redox Flow Batteries				
		User Group Organisations:		INESC TEC		Portugal
		Host Research Installation:		SYSLAB and Energy Systems Simulation Lab (DTU)		
		Access Status:		Completed		3 users
				Remote Access		5 access days
		Industry user project:	No			
Non-EU user project:		No	Internal-TA:	No	--- industry users	

4 Proposal Evaluation and User Selection Panel

4.1 Lab Access User Proposal Evaluation

The evaluation of the user project proposals in ERIGrid 2.0 was organised through two processes running in parallel: (1) pre-screening by the ERIGrid 2.0 laboratories, and (2) evaluation by the USP. The entire evaluation process was normally completed within 1-1.5 months after the deadline for the submission of proposals.

The pre-screening was the first assessment of the technical, economic, and organisational feasibility of the received proposal done by the three RIs selected (preferred) by the user group. Technical problems, risks, and related costs were considered. No further evaluation criteria were employed at this stage.

All received proposals have been evaluated by the USP following the principles of transparency, fairness, and impartiality. Each proposal was assessed by at least three experts of the USP. Except in some concrete cases, the ERIGrid 2.0 Lab Access Manager (i.e., J. Emilio Rodríguez) and the ERIGrid 2.0 Coordinator (i.e., Thomas Strasser) did not participate in the proposal evaluation, but were expected to overview the range of submitted proposals and to guarantee the compliance of the proposals with the eligibility rules of the lab access programme.

There were no meetings of the USP in ERIGrid 2.0; each USP member only kept a private interaction with the Project Coordinator and the Lab Access Manager, to avoid cross-influences in the evaluations with other USP members. The names of the USP members evaluating a proposal were not known by the proposing user group. On the contrary, the user group members and their organisations have been visible in the proposal to be evaluated by the USP (i.e., proposals had not been anonymised during their evaluation).

Each USP member reviewing a proposal evaluated the following categories:

1. *General quality of the proposal (score: 0-10)*: assessment based on the completeness and organisation of the proposal, clear definition of the objectives and expected results, relevance of the proposed dissemination actions, justified amount of access requested.
2. *Scientific/technical merit (score: 0-10)*: assessment based on the scientific and technical relevance, originality and innovation, methodology, robust and realistic test/evaluation approach.
3. *Improvement of know-how and capacity of the lab (score: 0-10)*: assessment based on the improvement of know-how within the laboratories, enhancement of lab technologies and methods, alignment with ERIGrid 2.0 scenarios/use cases/test cases, synergies with other projects and cooperation with other infrastructures.
4. *Compliance with EU policies and priorities (score: 0-10)*: assessment based on the compliance with European Research and Technological Development (RTD) policies and priorities, social impact, impact on EU industry (e.g., standardisation and competitiveness), sustainable growth interest, new users that have not previously used the installation, users working in countries where no equivalent RI exist, young researchers, female researchers.

For each proposal, the USP expert issued a score, which was the average of the scores of the four individual categories, expressed as total points out of 100. All categories had the same weight. The final score of the proposal has been calculated as the mean value of the scores issued by the USP members evaluating the proposal. Additionally, in this phase, the USP could

provide comments and suggestions to improve the project implementation in the lab (if the proposal was accepted in the end) or build a better proposal for resubmission to future calls (if the proposal was rejected in the corresponding call). A Proposal Review Report has been prepared based on the evaluation information of the USP members and sent to the user group when notifying them about the proposal evaluation result (accepted or rejected). An example of this Proposal Evaluation Report is included in the Appendix.

Besides the USP evaluation, all proposals have also been checked against plagiarism (in accordance to the general H2020 strategy³). Proposals with an unjustified high amount of similarity have not been considered for realisation and have been rejected.

4.2 User Selection Panel Membership

The USP was a group of a maximum of 133 members from international organisations (“external experts”) and from ERIGrid 2.0 partners (“internal experts”) with diverse profiles (academia, industry) and covering the different domains of the smart energy system arena (power systems, heating networks, Information and Communications Technology (ICT), cybersecurity, etc.).

The composition of the USP has been kept quite stable since it was created for the evaluation of the 1st call for lab access proposal in October 2020. There have been some replacements for different reasons: lack of real availability, retirement, movement to another institution, etc. At the finalisation of the project, the USP was formed by 72 external experts and 57 internal experts. The presence of “internal experts” has been advisable and contributed to assessing better if the received proposals were aligned with ERIGrid 2.0 approaches and goals.

The complete list of USP members contributing to the evaluation of the user proposals at some point during the duration of the lab access programme is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Membership of the ERIGrid 2.0 User Selection Panel.

EXTERNAL EXPERTS			
1	Abdulrahman Alassi	IBERDROLA	Qatar
2	Mihaela Albu	Politehnica University of Bucharest	Romania
3	João Francisco Alves Martins	Universidade Nova de Lisboa	Portugal
4	Reza Arghandeh	Western Norway University of Applied Sciences	Norway
5	Davood Babazadeh	Technische Universität Hamburg	Germany
6	Seddik Bacha	G2elab - UGA	France
7	Manuel Barragan-Villarejo	University of Seville	Spain
8	Andrea Benigni	Forschungszentrum Jülich and RWTH Aachen	Germany
9	Yvon Besanger-Moleres	Grenoble INP - UGA	France
10	Theo Bosma	DNVGL	Norway
11	Aggelos Bouhouras	Technological Educational Institute of Western Macedonia	Greece

³https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/checks-audits-reviews-investigations_en.htm

EXTERNAL EXPERTS

11	Aggelos Bouhouras	Technological Educational Institute of Western Macedonia	Greece
12	Jose Antonio Bregel	LCOE-FFII	Spain
13	Tiago Castelo de Oliveira	TU Eindhoven	Netherlands
14	Geraint Chaffey	KU Leuven	Belgium
15	Georgios C. Christoforidis	University of Western Macedonia	Greece
16	Giovanni De Carne	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	Germany
17	Marialaura Di Somma	ENEA	Italy
18	Luca Ferrarini	Politecnico di Milano	Italy
19	Davide Fioriti	Univesità di Pisa	Italy
20	Alemayehu Gebremedhin	Norwegian University of Science and Technology	Norway
21	Joern Geisbuesch	Academia	Germany
22	Murat Gol	Middle East Technical University	Turkey
23	Tasos Gregoriou	Distribution System Operator Cyprus	Cyprus
24	Efren Guillo Sansano	ENERCOOP	Spain
25	Ulf Häger	TU Dortmund	Germany
26	Trevor Hardy	Pacific Northwest National Laboratory	USA
27	Arjen Jongepier	Stedin	Netherlands
28	Petr Kadera	Czech Technical University in Prague	Czech Republic
29	Stavros Karagiannopoulos	ETH	Switzerland
30	Ata Khavari	SIEMENS	Germany
31	Heybet Kilic	Dicle University	Turkey
32	Nand Kishor	Ostfold University College	Norway
33	Thyge Knüppel	SIEMENS GAMESA	Denmark
34	Eleftherios Kontis	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	Greece
35	Anna Kosek	TNO	Belgium
36	Konstantinos Kotsalos	EUROPEAN DYNAMICS	Greece
37	Athanasios Krontiris	Hochschule Darmstadt University of Applied Sciences	Germany
38	Anna Kulmala	ABB	Finland
39	Hannu Laaksonen	University of Vaasa	Finland
40	Luiz Fernando Labado Villa	LAAS CNRS	France
41	Ilias Lamprinos	Intracom SA Telecom Solutions	Greece
42	Yannis Mantzaris	IPTO	Greece
43	Sergio Martinez	Technical University of Madrid	Spain
44	Jose Maria Maza-Ortega	University of Seville	Spain
45	Mark McGranaghan	EPRI	USA
46	Ali Mehrizi-Sani	Virginia Tech	USA
47	Mike Mekkanen	University of Vaasa	Finland
48	Konstantina Mentesidi	Cyprus Transmission System Operator	Greece
49	Andrea Morotti	Unareti	Italy
50	Panagiotis Moutis	Carnegie Mellon University	USA
51	Matija Naglic	TenneT TSO	Netherlands
52	Pedro Nardelli	LUT University	Finland

EXTERNAL EXPERTS

53	Tung Lam Nguyen	University of Science and Technology of Danang	Vietnam
54	Van Hoa Nguyen	EDF Lab Paris-Saclay	France
55	Artjoms Obusevs	Zurich University of Applied Science	Switzerland
56	Ioannis Panapakidis	University of Thessaly	Greece
57	Theofilos Papadopoulos	Democritus University of Thrace	Greece
58	Nick Papanikolaou	Democritus University of Thrace	Greece
59	Haris Patsios	University of Newcastle	United Kingdom
60	Luigi Piegari	DEIB - Politecnico di Milano	Italy
61	Mahdi Pourakbari Kasmaei	Aalto University	Finland
62	Edris Pouresmaeil	Aalto University	Finland
63	Victor Sanchez	MEGACAL INSTRUMENTS IBÉRICA	Spain
64	Mohamed Shalaby	Sono Motors GmbH	Germany
65	Pierluigi Siano	University of Salerno	Italy
66	Katja Sirviö	University of Vaasa	Finland
67	Spyros Skarvelis-Kazakos	University of Sussex	United Kingdom
68	Anurag Srivastava	Washington State University	USA
69	Andreas Stavrou	Electricity Authority of Cyprus	Cyprus
70	Yin Sun	Shell	Netherlands
71	Juergen Sutterlueti	Gantner Instruments GmbH	Austria
72	Petr Toman	Brno University of Technology	Czech Republic
73	Philip Top	Lawrence Livermore National Lab	USA
74	Xiaoyu Wang	Carleton University	Canada
75	Yu Wang	Nanyang Technological University	Singapore
76	Stephen Wolthusen	Norwegian University of Science and Technology	Norway
77	Dongsheng Yang	TU Eindhoven	Netherlands

INTERNAL EXPERTS

1	Ibrahim Abdulhadi	University of Strathclyde	United Kingdom
2	Gunter Arnold	Fraunhofer IEE	Germany
3	I. Safak Bayram	University of Strathclyde	United Kingdom
4	Henrik Bindner	Technical University of Denmark	Denmark
5	Ron Brandl	Fraunhofer IEE	Germany
6	Roland Bründlinger	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology	Austria
7	Hervé Buttin	CEA	France
8	Mihai Calin	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology	Austria
9	Salvador Ceballos	TECNALIA	Spain
10	Milos Cetkovic	TUD	Netherlands
11	Alexandros Chronis	ICCS-NTUA	Greece
12	Salvatore D'Arco	SINTEF Energi AS	Norway
13	Pratyush Das	OFFIS	Germany
14	Erik de Jong	KEMA	Netherlands
15	Venzelos Efthymiou	University of Cyprus	Cyprus
16	Corentin Evens	VTT	Finland

INTERNAL EXPERTS

17	Chiara Gandolfi	RSE	Italy
18	Oliver Gehrke	Technical University of Denmark	Denmark
19	George Georghiou	University of Cyprus	Cyprus
20	Ian Gilbert	OCT-Ormazabal	Spain
21	Amaia González-Garrido	TECNALIA	Spain
22	Wolfram Heckmann	Fraunhofer IEE	Germany
23	Kai Heussen	Technical University of Denmark	Denmark
24	Tran-The Hoang	CEA	France
25	Josu Izagirre	OCT-Ormazabal	Spain
26	Joseba Jimeno	TECNALIA	Spain
27	Jirapa Kamsamrong	OFFIS	Germany
28	Panagiotis Karafotis	HEDNO	Greece
29	Alkistis Kontou	ICCS-NTUA	Greece
30	Evangelos Kotsakis	Joint Research Centre of the European Commission	Italy
31	Panos Kotsampopoulos	ICCS-NTUA	Greece
32	Andreas Kyprianou	University of Cyprus	Cyprus
33	Georg Lauss	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology	Austria
34	Kari Mäki	VTT	Finland
35	Savvas Manikas	HEDNO	Greece
36	Olve Mo	SINTEF Energi AS	Norway
37	John Nikolettatos	CRES	Greece
38	Iñaki Orue	OCT-Ormazabal	Spain
39	Rafael Pena-Alzola	University of Strathclyde	United Kingdom
40	Marjan Popov	TUD	Netherlands
41	Filip Prössl Andrén	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology	Austria
42	Leonard Enrique Ramos Perez	DERlab e.V.	Germany
43	Kalle Rauma	VTT	Finland
44	Evangelos Rikos	CRES	Greece
45	Sebastian Rohjans	OFFIS / Jade University of Applied Science	Germany
46	Marco Rossi	RSE	Italy
47	Jose Rueda	TUD	Netherlands
48	Santiago Sánchez Acebedo	SINTEF Energi AS	Norway
49	Iolanda Saviuc	Joint Research Centre of the European Commission	Italy
50	Dimitrios Stratogiannis	HEDNO	Greece
51	Diana Strauss-Mincu	DERlab e.V.	Germany
52	Henning Taxt	SINTEF Energi AS	Norway
53	Carlo Tornelli	RSE	Italy
54	Quoc Tuan Tran	CEA	France
55	Peter Vaessen	KEMA	Netherlands
56	John Vlachos	CRES	Greece

4.3 User Selection Panel Evaluations of Lab Access Proposals

The following sections include the assignment of USP members to the proposals received in the lab access calls, and the corresponding scores cast by them. The aim was to have at least 3 evaluations per proposal to provide a balanced assessment, avoiding any individual bias.

4.3.1 Evaluation of 1st Call Proposals

The following list shows the evaluation results of the 1st call.

Overview of Reviews:		PMU-FFR				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Anurag Srivastava	Matija Naglic	Van Hoa Nguyen	Joern Geisbuesch		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	8	7	9		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	8	6	5		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	6	6	5		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	8	6	6	8		
General quality of the proposal	25%	6	10	6	6		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		65.63	67.50	75.00	60.00		

Overview of Reviews:		DEFINIT 2.0				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Andrea Benigni	Ulf Häger	Petr Toman	Yannis Mantzaris	Evangelos Rikos	
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		4	8	10	7	9	
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	4	8	9	10	
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	4	8	6	8	
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	6	7	7	9	
General quality of the proposal	25%	9	3	9	9	10	
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		73.5	75.00	42.50	80.00	92.50	

Overview of Reviews:		COLOURPOWER				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Mihai Calin	Philip Top	Filip Prössl Andrén	Andreas Kyprianou	Mihaela Albu	
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	3	4	7	9	
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	8	8	6	8	
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	8	7	7	9	
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	7	7	5	8	
General quality of the proposal	25%	10	8	10	6	10	
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		77	80.00	77.50	80.00	60.00	87.50

Overview of Reviews:		Autonom				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Nand Kishor</i>	<i>Yu Wang</i>	<i>Hannu Laaksonen</i>	<i>Joseba Jimeno</i>		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	8	8	8		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	2	8	8	9		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	4	8	8	9		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	4	6	7	8		
General quality of the proposal	25%	4	8	8	9		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	68.75	35.00	75.00	77.50	87.50		

Overview of Reviews:		POLARIS				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Nick Papanikolaou</i>	<i>Thyge Knüppel</i>	<i>Luigi Piegari</i>	<i>Jose Maria Maza-Ortega</i>	<i>Salvatore D'Arco</i>	
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	8	9	8	10	
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	8	9	9	8	
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	7	9	9	9	
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	4	7	9	9	6	
General quality of the proposal	25%	9	8	9	9	9	
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	81.5	72.50	75.00	90.00	90.00	80.00	

Overview of Reviews:		SES-MGES				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Luca Ferrarini</i>	<i>Wolfram Heckmann</i>	<i>Sebastian Rohjans</i>	<i>Petr Kadera</i>		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	5	8	7		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	5	9	8	1		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	8	9	1		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	7	6	0		
General quality of the proposal	25%	6	8	8	1		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	56.88	62.50	80.00	77.50	7.50		

Overview of Reviews:		Hytechnet				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Panagiotis Moutis</i>	<i>Arjen Jongepier</i>	<i>Mohamed Shalaby</i>	<i>Konstantina Mentesidi</i>		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		6	7	6	4		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	4	7	8	7		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	2	9	8	6		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	4	9	7	7		
General quality of the proposal	25%	1	6	7	8		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	62.5	27.50	77.50	75.00	70.00		

Overview of Reviews:		M-ECHall			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Mihai Calin	Heybet Kilic	Iolanda Saviuc	Luiz Fernando Labado Villa	Alexandros Chronis	Erik de Jong
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		9	10	8	8	9	9
Scientific/technical merit	25%	7	2	6	7	7	4
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	0	7	8	9	4
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	0	6	6	7	5
General quality of the proposal	25%	7	2	6	6	9	6
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		56.67	72.50	10.00	62.50	67.50	80.00

Overview of Reviews:		BAMLEV			NOT APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Ioannis Panapakidis	Artjoms Obusevs	Tasos Gregoriou	I Safak Bayram		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	7	7	8		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	5	6	4		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	3	8	6		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	3	7	3		
General quality of the proposal	25%	6	4	6	2		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		51.25	62.50	37.50	67.50		

Note: This proposal failed the plagiarism check.

Overview of Reviews:		RT-SimVal			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		João Francisco Alves Martins	Giovanni De Carne	Yvon Besanger-Moleres	Marjan Popov		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	8	8	10		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	5	4	8	7		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	5	6	8	7		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	5	7	6	6		
General quality of the proposal	25%	5	4	8	6		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		60.63	50.00	52.50	75.00		

Overview of Reviews:		OEM-MGR			NOT APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Mihai Calin	Xiaoyu Wang	Katja Sirviö	Antonios Marinopoulos		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	8	9	8		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	4	4	3	7		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	5	6	3	6		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	5	4	4	7		
General quality of the proposal	25%	4	4	3	6		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		46.88	45.00	45.00	32.50		

4.3.2 Evaluation of 2nd Call Proposals

The following list shows the evaluation results of the 2nd call.

Overview of Reviews:		DPSSEC			NOT APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Murat Gol</i>	<i>Ulf Häger</i>	<i>Savvas Manikas</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	8	4			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	4	5	5			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	5	7	7			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	6	9			
General quality of the proposal	25%	3	5	6			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		56.67	45.00	57.50			

Note: Proposal too vague for lab implementation. Important issues raised by the USP.

Overview of Reviews:		PROOF			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Luiz Fernando Labado Villa</i>	<i>Tran-The Hoang</i>	<i>Evangelos Rikos</i>	<i>Wolfram Heckmann</i>		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	9	7	8		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	6	10	7		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	6	8	8		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	7	9	7		
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	6	9	8		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		74.38	70.00	62.50	90.00	75.00	

Overview of Reviews:		VoIDIP			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Panagiotis Moutis</i>	<i>Giovanni De Carne</i>	<i>Amaia González-Garrido</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	9	8			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	4	9			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	4	8			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	5	6			
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	4	8			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		65	75.00	42.50	77.50		

Overview of Reviews:		DeMaDsVal				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		João Francisco Alves Martins	Philip Top	Petr Toman	Ata Khavari		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	6	8	6		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	10	6	8	8		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	10	7	8	8		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	8	6	7	7		
General quality of the proposal	25%	10	8	8	10		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		80.63	95.00	67.50	77.50	82.50	

Overview of Reviews:		GRIDPV100				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Iolanda Saviuc	Georgios C. Christoforidis	Edris Pouresmaeil	Jose Maria Maza-Ortega	Mihaela Albu	
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		6	8	10	9	9	
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	9	5	7	9	
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	8	7	8	8	
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	8	4	9	7	
General quality of the proposal	25%	7	9	5	8	9	
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		74.5	72.50	85.00	52.50	80.00	82.50

Overview of Reviews:		DynOMO				NOT APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Yannis Mantzaris	Theofilos Papadopoulos	Erik de Jong			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		6	7	9			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	7	5	4			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	8	2			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	8	6	4			
General quality of the proposal	25%	6	4	2			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		53.33	72.50	57.50	30.00		

Note: Proposal not ready for lab implementation yet. Important issues raised by the USP.

Overview of Reviews:		SIM HES-OFF				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Andrea Benigni	Van Hoa Nguyen	Eleftherios Kontis	Petr Kadera		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	10	7	8		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	4	6	8	8		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	6	8	8		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	6	6	8		
General quality of the proposal	25%	7	8	10	9		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		71.88	60.00	65.00	80.00	82.50	

Overview of Reviews:		PPiF			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Artjoms Obusevs	Kostas Anastasakis	Venizelos Efthymiou			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	6	10			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	10	5			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	10	4			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	9	5			
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	10	5			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		70.83	67.50	47.50			

Overview of Reviews:		Open-CANVerter			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Luca Ferrarini	Mike Mekkanen	Yu Wang	Spyros Skarvelis-Kazakos	Evangelos Kotsakis	
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	8	8	8	9	
Scientific/technical merit	25%	5	9	6	8	9	
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	9	7	7	8	
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	7	7	6	8	
General quality of the proposal	25%	9	9	6	8	9	
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		76	72.50	85.00	65.00	72.50	85.00

Overview of Reviews:		VaFlexPot			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Katja Sirviö	Yin Sun	Georg Lauss			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	6	9			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	6	8			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	9	6	9			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	2	6			
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	6	8			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		69.17	80.00	50.00	77.50		

Overview of Reviews:		CREAM			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Ioannis Panapakidis	Davood Babazadeh	Tasos Gregoriou	Filip Prössl Andrén		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		6	9	7	7		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	6	9	8		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	7	9	8		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	8	7	9	6		
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	8	10	8		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		79.38	80.00	70.00	92.50	75.00	

Overview of Reviews:		PvinPS				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Arjen Jongepier</i>	<i>Luigi Piegari</i>	<i>Juergen Sutterlueti</i>	<i>Anna Kulmala</i>		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	9	6	6		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	6	5	7		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	8	5	7		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	7	5	8		
General quality of the proposal	25%	7	7	5	8		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	65.63	67.50	70.00	50.00	75.00		

Overview of Reviews:		resiMG				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Yvon Besanger-Moleres</i>	<i>Nick Papanikolaou</i>	<i>Nand Kishor</i>	<i>Hannu Laaksonen</i>		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	9	8	9		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	10	7	6	4		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	10	8	8	5		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	6	6	4		
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	9	8	3		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	68.13	87.50	75.00	70.00	40.00		

4.3.3 Evaluation of 3rd Call Proposals

The following list shows the evaluation results of the 3rd call.

Overview of Reviews:		PETER			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Matija Naglic</i>	<i>Georgios C. Christoforidis</i>	<i>Ian Gilbert</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		4	8	7			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	7	7			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	6	6	7			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	8	6	6			
General quality of the proposal	25%	2	5	6			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	61.67	60.00	60.00	65.00			

Overview of Reviews:		FLEVOEWIM			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
			<i>João Francisco Alves Martins</i>	<i>Luca Ferrarini</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	6	8			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	7	7	9			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	7	8			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	7	7			
General quality of the proposal	25%	7	9	9			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		75	67.50	75.00	82.50		

Overview of Reviews:		VEHICLE			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
			<i>Nick Papanikolaou</i>	<i>Xiaoyu Wang</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		9	7	8			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	9	4	6			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	9	6	5			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	8	6	6			
General quality of the proposal	25%	10	6	4			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		65.83	90.00	55.00	52.50		

4.3.4 Evaluation of 4th Call Proposals

The following list shows the evaluation results of the 4th call.

Overview of Reviews:		PMUs-Cloud			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
			<i>Matija Naglic</i>	<i>Eleftherios Kontis</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	9	9	8	10	
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	8	3	8	9	
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	6	8	4	6	9	
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	6	6	8	7	
General quality of the proposal	25%	7	8	2	8	5	
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		65	62.50	75.00	37.50	75.00	75.00

Overview of Reviews:		VOLTMETER			NOT APPROVED		
		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
Questions		Mihai Calin	I Safak Bayram	Anna Kulmala			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	6	10			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	5	5	5			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	5	4	6			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	5	5	6			
General quality of the proposal	25%	5	5	6			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	51.67	50.00	47.50	57.50			

Note: Important issues raised by the USP do not allow the lab implementation.

Overview of Reviews:		DynOMO			APPROVED		
		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
Questions		Mihai Calin	Theofilos Papadopoulos	Gunter Arnold			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	7	7			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	6	7			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	8	8			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	7	6			
General quality of the proposal	25%	7	6	6			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	67.5	67.50	67.50	67.50			

Overview of Reviews:		AIDGRIDS			APPROVED		
		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
Questions		Murat Gol	Sebastian Rohjans	Amaia González-Garrido			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	7	9			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	9	10			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	10	8			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	5	8	7			
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	10	9			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	80.83	65.00	92.50	85.00			

Overview of Reviews:		CybTEST			APPROVED		
		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
Questions		Davood Babazadeh	Artjoms Obusevs	John Nikoletatos	Ata Khavari		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		9	6	8	6		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	6	6	7		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	9	6	7	7		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	8	6	7	7		
General quality of the proposal	25%	9	7	8	7		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	71.88	85.00	62.50	70.00	70.00		

Overview of Reviews:		LD-RTCosim					APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6	
		Van Hoa Nguyen	Georg Lauss	Ron Brandl	Alkistis Kontou	Joern Geisbuesch	Efren Guillo Sansano	
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		9	10	8	9	8	10	
Scientific/technical merit	25%	7	7	7	7	4	7	
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	6	8	9	3	8	
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	5	6	6	6	4	6	
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	8	4	10	3	8	
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		64.58	70.00	67.50	62.50	80.00	35.00	72.50

Overview of Reviews:		SMPS				APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6	
		Katja Sirviö	Tasos Gregoriou	Hannu Laaksonen	Tran-The Hoang	Rafael Pena-Alzola	Ibrahim Abdulhadi	
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	6	8	8	9	8	
Scientific/technical merit	25%	3	9	7	7	2	7	
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	5	9	7	7	1	8	
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	7	6	9	2	6	
General quality of the proposal	25%	6	8	8	6	1	7	
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		60.42	52.50	82.50	70.00	72.50	15.00	70.00

Overview of Reviews:		AGIPDem					APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6	
		Giovanni De Carne	Seddik Bacha	Jose Maria Maza-Ortega	Iñaki Orue	Salvador Ceballos		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	7	8	8	5		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	9	8	7	5	7		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	8	7	8	8		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	6	7	5	7		
General quality of the proposal	25%	9	7	7	7	7		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		72	82.50	72.50	70.00	62.50	72.50	

Overview of Reviews:		HCEQIS				NOT APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6	
		Heybet Kilic	Luiz Fernando Labado Villa	Nand Kishor	Tran-The Hoang			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	9	8	6			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	4	4	4			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	6	4	7	4			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	4	4	6	6			
General quality of the proposal	25%	4	5	6	4			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		48.75	50.00	42.50	57.50	45.00		

Overview of Reviews:		RCPIso					APPROVED
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Yvon Besanger-Moleres	Iolanda Saviuc	Pedro Nardelli	Kostas Anastasakis	Carlo Tomelli	
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		6	8	9	6	10	
Scientific/technical merit	25%	4	6	6	7	6	
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	6	8	7	6	4	
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	5	6	7	5	3	
General quality of the proposal	25%	5	6	7	7	7	
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	59	50.00	65.00	67.50	62.50	50.00	

Overview of Reviews:		IoRE			NOT APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Edris Pouresmaeil	Henning Taxt	Venizelos Efthymiou			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	6	8			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	9	1	2			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	2	4			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	8	2	4			
General quality of the proposal	25%	9	2	3			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	45	85.00	17.50	32.50			

Overview of Reviews:		IC2PSofMG					APPROVED
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Luca Ferrarini	Nick Papanikolaou	Chiara Gandolfi	Marco Rossi	Amaia González-Garrido	
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	10	9	7	9	
Scientific/technical merit	25%	5	6	5	6	4	
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	6	7	5	7	7	
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	5	6	5	6	6	
General quality of the proposal	25%	6	7	7	7	5	
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	59	55.00	65.00	55.00	65.00	55.00	

Overview of Reviews:		SEFL EMTR			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Ulf Häger	Sergio Martinez	Erik de Jong			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	6	6			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	9	9	7			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	9	8	7			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	9	7	9			
General quality of the proposal	25%	9	9	9			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	84.17	90.00	82.50	80.00			

Overview of Reviews:		TRMDRO				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		João Francisco Alves Martins	Luigi Piegari	Mohamed Shalaby	Kari Máki		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	10	5	8		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	7	9	7		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	6	9	8		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	8	8	7		
General quality of the proposal	25%	9	7	6	8		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		75.63	77.50	70.00	80.00	75.00	

Overview of Reviews:		CYPRESS			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Evangelos Rikos	Gianluca Fulli	Petr Kadera			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	6	8			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	9	8	8			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	9	8	6			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	8	7	7			
General quality of the proposal	25%	9	7	7			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		77.5	87.50	75.00	70.00		

Overview of Reviews:		RELENDER				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Andrea Benigni	Filip Prösti/Andrén	Panos Kotsampopoulos	Andreas Kyprianou		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	8	6	7		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	9	8	8		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	6	8	7	9		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	8	7	8		
General quality of the proposal	25%	4	9	7	8		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		73.75	85.00	72.50	82.50		

4.3.5 Evaluation of 5th Call Proposals

The following list shows the evaluation results of the 5th call.

Overview of Reviews:		Grid ExpanDER			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Murat Gol</i>	<i>Petr Toman</i>	<i>Theofilos Papadopoulos</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		9	8	7			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	8	5			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	8	6			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	8	5			
General quality of the proposal	25%	10	8	4			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		70.83	82.50	80.00	50.00		

Overview of Reviews:		CPHILT-GFVSC				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Georg Lauss</i>	<i>Salvatore D'Arco</i>	<i>Erik de Jong</i>	<i>Amaia González-Garrido</i>		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	10	10	8		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	7	8	9	8		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	6	7	8	9		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	7	7	6		
General quality of the proposal	25%	7	9	9	8		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		76.25	67.50	77.50	82.50	77.50	

Overview of Reviews:		PHIL-Rep			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Van Hoa Nguyen</i>	<i>Georg Lauss</i>	<i>Joern Geisbuesch</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		9	10	10			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	4	7	5			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	2	8	6			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	6	8			
General quality of the proposal	25%	4	7	7			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		58.33	40.00	70.00	65.00		

Overview of Reviews:		EMS4GCHS				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Panagiotis Moutis	Mike Mekkanen	Tasos Gregoriou	Spyros Skarvelis-Kazakos		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	8	7	8		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	2	4	6	8		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	4	4	7	7		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	2	6	7	7		
General quality of the proposal	25%	0	4	6	7		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		50.63	20.00	45.00	65.00	72.50	

Overview of Reviews:		HIHREMS			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Luiz Fernando Labado Villa	Evangelos Rikos	Alkistis Kontou			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	10	7			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	3	7	7			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	1	7	7			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	2	8	8			
General quality of the proposal	25%	1	7	8			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		55	17.50	72.50	75.00		

Overview of Reviews:		ProMiSe				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Xiaoyu Wang	Arjen Jongepier	Artjoms Obusevs	Anna Kulmala		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	10	8	9		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	8	7	7		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	10	8	8		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	8	8	7	6		
General quality of the proposal	25%	9	10	8	8		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		80	82.50	90.00	75.00	72.50	

Overview of Reviews:		PERFECT				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Luca Ferrarini	Ulf Häger	Reza Arghandeh	Salvador Ceballos	Erik de Jong	
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		6	8	9	5	10	
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	6	6	7	6	
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	8	7	7	5	
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	5	6	6	7	6	
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	6	7	4	7	
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		63.5	65.00	65.00	65.00	62.50	60.00

Overview of Reviews:		CyDERFORT				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Davood Babazadeh</i>	<i>Pedro Nardelli</i>	<i>Georg Lauss</i>	<i>Sebastian Rohjans</i>		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	8	5	6		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	9	6	8		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	9	6	8		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	9	6	7		
General quality of the proposal	25%	9	9	6	9		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	77.5	80.00	90.00	60.00	80.00		

Overview of Reviews:		IETGPSC			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Iolanda Saviuc</i>	<i>Nand Kishor</i>	<i>Sergio Martinez</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	8	7			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	2	5			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	4	5			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	3	7			
General quality of the proposal	25%	6	2	6			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	49.17	62.50	27.50	57.50			

Overview of Reviews:		Dyn-PEM				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Giovanni De Came</i>	<i>Yvon Besanger-Moleres</i>	<i>Luigi Piegari</i>	<i>Eleftherios Kontis</i>	<i>Hannu Laaksonen</i>	
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	8	8	8	8	
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	8	4	6	5	
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	6	8	4	5	5	
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	6	6	5	5	
General quality of the proposal	25%	6	8	4	5	6	
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	57	60.00	75.00	45.00	52.50	52.50	

Overview of Reviews:		Multigradcon			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Nick Papanikolaou</i>	<i>Heybet Kilic</i>	<i>Yu Wang</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	10	9			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	7	6	6			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	6	7			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	6	5			
General quality of the proposal	25%	7	6	6			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	63.33	70.00	60.00	60.00			

4.3.6 Evaluation of 6th Call Proposals

The following list shows the evaluation results of the 6th call.

Overview of Reviews:		TRMDRO			APPROVED		
		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
Questions		<i>João Francisco Alves Martins</i>	<i>Evangelos Rikos</i>	<i>Panos Kotsampopoulos</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	8	5			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	9	7			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	6	8	5			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	5	7	5			
General quality of the proposal	25%	7	7	8			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		66.67	60.00	77.50			

Overview of Reviews:		ISAIPS			APPROVED		
		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
Questions		<i>Ulf Häger</i>	<i>Xiaoyu Wang</i>	<i>Philip Top</i>	<i>Aggelos Bouhouras</i>	<i>Dongsheng Yang</i>	
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		6	6	4	7	10	
Scientific/technical merit	25%	9	8	6	9	8	
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	7	6	8	7	
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	9	8	6	8	7	
General quality of the proposal	25%	9	8	6	8	8	
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		76.5	87.50	77.50	60.00	82.50	75.00

Overview of Reviews:		FaultTS			APPROVED		
		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
Questions		<i>Petr Toman</i>	<i>Theofilos Papadopoulos</i>	<i>Marjan Popov</i>	<i>Ian Gilbert</i>		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	7	9	8		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	6	6	8		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	7	7	7		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	5	7	7		
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	4	7	9		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		67.5	70.00	55.00	67.50	77.50	

Overview of Reviews:		Sono LV-MCU				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Luiz Fernando Labado Villa</i>	<i>Georg Lauss</i>	<i>Alkistis Kontou</i>	<i>Erik de Jong</i>	<i>Marialaura Di Somma</i>	
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	8	8	10	8	
Scientific/technical merit	25%	7	8	8	3	8	
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	6	8	8	2	8	
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	7	9	5	6	
General quality of the proposal	25%	7	8	9	5	8	
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	68	65.00	77.50	85.00	37.50	75.00	

Overview of Reviews:		CTCPM				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Ali Mehrizi-Sani</i>	<i>Heybet Kilic</i>	<i>Wolfram Heckmann</i>	<i>Jirapa Kamsamrong</i>	<i>Davide Fioriti</i>	
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	8	4	6	4	
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	4	7	8	7	
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	4	7	8	6	
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	4	7	7	6	
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	6	7	9	6	
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	67	77.50	45.00	70.00	80.00	62.50	

Overview of Reviews:		CYPRESS-Wood				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Athanasios Krontiris</i>	<i>Manuel Barragan-Villarejo</i>	<i>Trevor Hardy</i>	<i>Konstantinos Kotsalos</i>		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		6	8	9	8		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	7	7	5	9		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	8	4	9		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	6	6	8		
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	8	6	9		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	71.88	75.00	72.50	52.50	87.50		

4.3.7 Evaluation of 7th Call Proposals

The following list shows the evaluation results of the 7th call.

Overview of Reviews:		BCF			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Mihai Calin</i>	<i>Filip Prössl Andrén</i>	<i>Alkistis Kontou</i>	<i>Santiago Sánchez Acevedo</i>		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	8	6	8		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	7	6	8		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	6	6	8	7		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	5	6	6	6		
General quality of the proposal	25%	7	6	6	8		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		65	60.00	62.50	65.00	72.50	

Overview of Reviews:		PROTECT			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Hannu Laaksonen</i>	<i>Rafael Pena-Alzola</i>	<i>Mihaela Albu</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		9	6	9			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	4	5	7			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	5	7	8			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	5	6	7			
General quality of the proposal	25%	5	7	8			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		61.67	47.50	62.50	75.00		

Overview of Reviews:		ITCMPD			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Erik de Jong</i>	<i>Jose Antonio Bregel</i>	<i>Geraint Chaffey</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	9	6			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	9	5			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	10	6			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	8	10	6			
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	10	5			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		76.67	77.50	97.50	55.00		

Overview of Reviews:		ColdHarmonics				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Olve Mo</i>	<i>Amaja González-Garrido</i>	<i>Mahdi Pourakbari Kasmaei</i>	<i>Tiago Elias Castelo de Oliveira</i>		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	8	8	9		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	5	9	9	8		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	4	6	8	8		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	5	8	7	6		
General quality of the proposal	25%	2	8	9	8		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	68.75	40.00	77.50	82.50	75.00		

Overview of Reviews:		IsMAER				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Yvon Besanger-Moleres</i>	<i>Spyros Skarvelis-Kazakos</i>	<i>Evangelos Rikos</i>	<i>Joseba Jimeno</i>	<i>Kari Mäki</i>	<i>Petr Kadera</i>
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	8	8	8	9	7
Scientific/technical merit	25%	4	7	8	4	8	4
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	7	8	5	6	6
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	7	9	7	8	8
General quality of the proposal	25%	6	6	8	4	8	5
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	65.83	62.50	67.50	82.50	50.00	75.00	57.50

Overview of Reviews:		E2MPC				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Murat Gol</i>	<i>Giovanni De Carne</i>	<i>Jose Maria Maza-Ortega</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	9	6			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	4	5	8			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	5	6	8			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	5	9			
General quality of the proposal	25%	3	5	8			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	60	45.00	52.50	82.50			

Overview of Reviews:		EMPC-DC				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Heybet Kilic</i>	<i>Davood Babazadeh</i>	<i>Luigi Piegari</i>	<i>Van Hoa Nguyen</i>	<i>Alkistis Kontou</i>	<i>Kalle Rauma</i>
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	10	10	8	7	7
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	7	4	5	7	9
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	6	7	2	2	7	9
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	7	8	6	7	8
General quality of the proposal	25%	6	8	3	4	6	10
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	62.5	60.00	72.50	42.50	42.50	67.50	90.00

Overview of Reviews:		HVLD				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Theofilos Papadopoulos</i>	<i>Ian Gilbert</i>	<i>Iñaki Orue</i>	<i>Abdulrahman Alassi</i>		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	8	9	7		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	5	8	9	6		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	9	7	6		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	6	7	7		
General quality of the proposal	25%	4	8	8	6		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	68.75	57.50	77.50	77.50	62.50		

Overview of Reviews:		EnergyCom				NOT APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Artjoms Obusevs</i>	<i>Alexandros Chronis</i>	<i>Corentin Evens</i>	<i>Marialaura Di Somma</i>		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	9	9	10		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	2	8	5	8		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	1	7	4	8		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	0	8	9	9		
General quality of the proposal	25%	2	8	3	8		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	56.25	12.50	77.50	52.50	82.50		

Note: Proposal too vague for lab implementation. Important issues raised by the USP.

Overview of Reviews:		POEM			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Ali Mehrizi-Sani</i>	<i>Oliver Gehrke</i>	<i>Salvatore D'Arco</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	9	10			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	8	8			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	5	7	8			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	4	6	7			
General quality of the proposal	25%	2	9	9			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	65.83	42.50	75.00	80.00			

Overview of Reviews:		CO-FLEX			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Kai Heussen</i>	<i>I Safak Bayram</i>	<i>Trevor Hardy</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	8	9			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	9	7			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	8	8			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	9	6			
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	8	8			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	75.83	70.00	85.00	72.50			

Overview of Reviews:		MOTIVATION-ERA			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Gunter Arnold</i>	<i>Henning Taxt</i>	<i>Salvador Ceballos</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	7	8			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	8	5			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	6	7			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	7	8			
General quality of the proposal	25%	6	8	3			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	64.17	62.50	72.50	57.50			

Overview of Reviews:		MOTIVATION- ISLE			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Alkistis Kontou</i>	<i>Anna Kulmala</i>	<i>Athanasios Krontiris</i>	<i>Konstantinos Kotsalos</i>		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	8	6	8		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	7	6	5		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	7	8	8		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	8	7	7	9		
General quality of the proposal	25%	10	7	7	7		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	74.38	85.00	70.00	70.00	72.50		

Overview of Reviews:		ABILITY			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Panagiotis Moutis</i>	<i>Evangelos Rikos</i>	<i>Carlo Tornelli</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	9	7			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	4	10	8			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	4	9	8			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	4	9	7			
General quality of the proposal	25%	2	10	9			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	70	35.00	95.00	80.00			

Overview of Reviews:		PVIPSFS			NOT APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Ulf Häger</i>	<i>Xiaoyu Wang</i>	<i>Marco Rossi</i>	<i>Erik de Jong</i>	<i>Manuel Barragan-Villarejo</i>	
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	5	8	10	7	
Scientific/technical merit	25%	5	4	8	2	3	
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	4	5	8	2	4	
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	5	6	9	4	4	
General quality of the proposal	25%	3	4	6	2	2	
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	45	42.50	47.50	77.50	25.00	32.50	

Overview of Reviews:		ESS-IMG2C-PVoF				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Nick Papanikolaou	Nand Kishor	Andreas Kyprianou	Aggelos Bouhouras		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	8	8	9		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	7	4	7	4		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	8	8	4		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	6	7	5		
General quality of the proposal	25%	7	4	8	2		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	59.38	70.00	55.00	75.00	37.50		

Overview of Reviews:		GGWO-TSKFS-CoGCHRESB				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Xiaoyu Wang	Arjen Jongepier	Luigi Piegari	Filip Prössl Andrén		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	8	9	8		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	3	4	8	6		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	5	6	9	6		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	2	5	10	6		
General quality of the proposal	25%	4	2	9	7		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	57.5	35.00	42.50	90.00	62.50		

Overview of Reviews:		HFMP4STVSI				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Nick Papanikolaou	Roland Bründlinger	Salvatore D'Arco			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		6	8	9			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	5	8	5			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	6	8	6			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	6	6			
General quality of the proposal	25%	7	8	4			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	63.33	62.50	75.00	52.50			

Overview of Reviews:		MOFOM PV				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Petr Toman	John Nikolettatos	Mohamed Shalaby			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	9	8			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	6	9			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	9	7	10			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	7	10			
General quality of the proposal	25%	9	9	9			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	83.33	82.50	72.50	95.00			

Overview of Reviews:		MOVES			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Ulf Häger</i>	<i>Ata Khavari</i>	<i>Jirapa Kamsamrong</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	7	6			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	9	9			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	9	8	10			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	8	7	8			
General quality of the proposal	25%	9	9	9			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	85.83	85.00	82.50	90.00			

Overview of Reviews:		IES-MG			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Heybet Kilic</i>	<i>Nand Kishor</i>	<i>Sebastian Rohjans</i>	<i>Leonard Enrique Ramos Perez</i>		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	6	6	8		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	6	5	8		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	6	8	6	8		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	8	6	8		
General quality of the proposal	25%	6	6	6	9		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	67.5	60.00	70.00	57.50	82.50		

Overview of Reviews:		PLANREC			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Iolanda Saviuc</i>	<i>Katja Sirviö</i>	<i>Henrik Bindner</i>	<i>Mohamed Shalaby</i>	<i>Venizelos Eftthymiou</i>	
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	7	8	8	9	
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	5	5	10	8	
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	4	3	9	10	
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	5	6	8	9	
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	6	4	8	10	
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	69.5	72.50	50.00	45.00	87.50	92.50	

Overview of Reviews:		Energética2031			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Petr Toman</i>	<i>Wolfram Heckmann</i>	<i>Ibrahim Abdulhadi</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	8	9			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	9	7			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	6	8	6			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	8	7			
General quality of the proposal	25%	5	9	8			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	72.5	62.50	85.00	70.00			

Overview of Reviews:		PHIL-1phGFVSC				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Ron Brandl	Joern Geisbuesch	Efren Guillo Sansano	Dongsheng Yang		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	8	8	10		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	5	6	8	4		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	6	5	8	6		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	3	5	7	3		
General quality of the proposal	25%	6	6	10	4		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	57.5	50.00	55.00	82.50	42.50		

4.3.8 Evaluation of 8th Call Proposals

The following list shows the evaluation results of the 8th call.

Overview of Reviews:		iniTiate				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Yvon Besanger-Moleres	Reza Arghandeh	Alkistis Kontou	Manuel Barragan-Villarejo		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	9	10	10		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	10	5	9	9		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	10	7	10	9		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	8	6	9	7		
General quality of the proposal	25%	10	6	10	10		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	84.38	95.00	60.00	95.00	87.50		

Overview of Reviews:		IMSPS				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Ulf Häger	Leonard Enrique Ramos Perez	Aggelos Bouhouras			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	9	8			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	9	9	8			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	9	8			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	8	7	9			
General quality of the proposal	25%	9	10	9			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	85.83	85.00	87.50	85.00			

Overview of Reviews:		WindGrid				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Katja Sirviö	Spyros Skarvelis-Kazakos	Evangelos Rikos	Kari Mäki	Petr Kadera	
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	8	10	9	6	
Scientific/technical merit	25%	4	5	8	8	5	
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	7	8	8	6	
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	6	7	8	6	
General quality of the proposal	25%	6	6	9	8	6	
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	67	57.50	60.00	80.00	80.00	57.50	

Overview of Reviews:		AID4EPES				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Heybet Kilic	Philip Top	Nand Kishor	Sebastian Rohjans		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	5	8	7		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	6	8	10		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	6	7	7	9		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	6	8	8		
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	8	8	10		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	75.63	65.00	67.50	77.50	92.50		

Overview of Reviews:		VISION				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Davood Babazadeh	Van Hoa Nguyen	Alexandros Chronis	Davide Floriti		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		9	8	6	8		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	9	5	9	8		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	5	8	8		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	4	8	7		
General quality of the proposal	25%	9	5	9	9		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	73.75	82.50	47.50	85.00	80.00		

Overview of Reviews:		DEFENSE				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Theofilos Papadopoulos	Ibrahim Abdulhadi	Geraint Chaffey			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	8	8			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	6	3			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	6	4			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	5	6	7			
General quality of the proposal	25%	5	6	4			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	55	60.00	60.00	45.00			

Overview of Reviews:		TwinNET				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Marco Rossi	Anna Kulmala	Amaia González-Garrido	Konstantinos Kotsalos		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	6	7	8		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	8	10	8		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	7	9	8		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	8	7	8	8		
General quality of the proposal	25%	9	8	10	8		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	82.5	82.50	75.00	92.50	80.00		

Overview of Reviews:		DDPAOP				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Petr Toman	Hannu Laaksonen	Pratyush Das			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		9	8	7			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	6	8			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	6	7			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	8	5	7			
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	5	9			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	70.83	80.00	55.00	77.50			

Overview of Reviews:		DRLeMPC4RVFSinMG				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Nick Papanikolaou	Filip Prössl Andrén	Andreas Kyprianou			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		9	8	8			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	5	8	8			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	8	7			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	8	6			
General quality of the proposal	25%	7	9	8			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	73.33	65.00	82.50	72.50			

Overview of Reviews:		M4Grid				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Jose Maria Maza-Ortega	Ian Gilbert	Mihaela Albu			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	6	10			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	7	6	7			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	7	6			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	8	6	6			
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	7	8			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	70	77.50	65.00	67.50			

Overview of Reviews:		RTT-Flow			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Erik de Jong</i>	<i>Amaia González-Garrido</i>	<i>Mahdi Pourakbari Kasmaei</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	8	8			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	10	10	9			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	9	7	8			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	8	8	7			
General quality of the proposal	25%	10	8	9			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	85.83	92.50	82.50	82.50			

Overview of Reviews:		DTCPMSMDRA			NOT APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Luiz Fernando Labado Villa</i>	<i>Alkistis Kontou</i>	<i>Erik de Jong</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		6	6	9			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	4	9	5			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	4	8	2			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	4	8	3			
General quality of the proposal	25%	1	10	5			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	52.5	32.50	87.50	37.50			

Note: Important issues raised by the USP do not allow the lab implementation.

Overview of Reviews:		DiSeCTER			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Filip Prösl Andrén</i>	<i>Carlo Tomelli</i>	<i>Jirapa Kamsamrong</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	8	10			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	7	8			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	8	9			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	8	7	9			
General quality of the proposal	25%	9	8	9			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	81.67	82.50	75.00	87.50			

Overview of Reviews:		FOSTER			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Artjoms Obusevs</i>	<i>Evangelos Rikos</i>	<i>Joern Geisbuesch</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	9	8			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	8	5			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	8	5			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	7	6			
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	9	5			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	69.17	75.00	80.00	52.50			

Overview of Reviews:		CGNN4Grid			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Arjen Jongepier	Ron Brandl	Amaia González-Garrido			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	7	8			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	8	9			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	6	6			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	5	7	7			
General quality of the proposal	25%	9	7	8			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	72.5	72.50	70.00	75.00			

4.3.9 Evaluation of 9th Call Proposals

The following list shows the evaluation results of the 9th call.

Overview of Reviews:		IaaS Platform			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Filip Pröbstl Andrén	Evangelos Rikos	Trevor Hardy			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	8	9			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	10	6			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	9	5			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	9	6			
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	9	6			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	75.83	77.50	92.50	57.50			

Overview of Reviews:		RTPIM			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Heybet Kilic	Nand Kishor	Hannu Laaksonen	Mihaela Albu		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	8	7	8		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	8	5	8		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	6	8	5	8		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	4	4	5	8		
General quality of the proposal	25%	6	8	5	9		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	64.38	55.00	70.00	50.00	82.50		

Overview of Reviews:		EVEREST			APPROVED		
		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
Questions		<i>Katja Sirviö</i>	<i>Spyros Skarvelis-Kazakos</i>	<i>Jose Maria Maza-Ortega</i>	<i>Aggelos Bouhouras</i>	<i>Mahdi Pourakbari Kasmaei</i>	
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	9	8	9	8	
Scientific/technical merit	25%	3	10	6	7	8	
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	9	6	8	8	
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	10	6	8	9	
General quality of the proposal	25%	3	9	6	7	7	
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	72	50.00	95.00	60.00	75.00	80.00	

Overview of Reviews:		RCPIN			APPROVED		
		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
Questions		<i>Petr Toman</i>	<i>Anna Kulmala</i>	<i>Manuel Barragan-Villarejo</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		9	9	8			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	7	6	3			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	7	8			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	7	8			
General quality of the proposal	25%	7	7	4			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	65	70.00	67.50	57.50			

Overview of Reviews:		HYPO			NOT APPROVED		
		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
Questions		<i>Arjen Jongepier</i>	<i>Luigi Piegari</i>	<i>Artjoms Obusevs</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	9	8			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	3	7	4			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	2	9	2			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	4	9	4			
General quality of the proposal	25%	2	7	4			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	47.5	27.50	80.00	35.00			

4.3.10 Evaluation of 10th Call Proposals

The following list shows the evaluation results of the 10th call.

Overview of Reviews:		Early Fault Monitoring			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		J. Emilio Rodriguez-Seco	Georgios C. Christoforidis	Erik de Jong			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	7	6			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	7	8	8			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	8	6			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	8	6			
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	8	8			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	75	75.00	80.00	70.00			

Overview of Reviews:		EXPLORE-MP3S			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Luca Ferrarini	Edris Pouresmaeil	Gunter Arnold	Manuel Barragan-Villarejo		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		6	10	6	8		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	7	8	9	8		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	6	9	9	8		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	8	8	6		
General quality of the proposal	25%	7	9	9	7		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	77.5	65.00	85.00	87.50	72.50		

Overview of Reviews:		RESIDE			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Artjoms Obusevs	Roland Bründlinger	Aggelos Bouhouras			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	8	9			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	7	8	8			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	9	8			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	8	8	8			
General quality of the proposal	25%	7	10	8			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	80.83	75.00	87.50	80.00			

Overview of Reviews:		RECDT			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Luiz Fernando Labado Villa</i>	<i>Filip Pröbstl Andrén</i>	<i>Athanasios Krontiris</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		9	8	7			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	4	6	8			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	1	6	9			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	2	8	10			
General quality of the proposal	25%	2	6	9			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	59.17	22.50	65.00	90.00			

Overview of Reviews:		DevA-PHIL			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Davood Babazadeh</i>	<i>Ron Brandl</i>	<i>Alkistis Kontou</i>	<i>Joern Geisbuesch</i>		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		9	9	10	10		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	9	6	7	10		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	9	6	8	6		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	9	5	8	5		
General quality of the proposal	25%	10	6	8	9		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	75.63	92.50	57.50	77.50	75.00		

Overview of Reviews:		DRE4BalanceReserve			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Spyros Skarvelis-Kazakos</i>	<i>Evangelos Rikos</i>	<i>Mahdi Pourakbari Kasmaei</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	9	8			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	9	9	7			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	8	8			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	8	9	6			
General quality of the proposal	25%	9	7	8			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	80	85.00	82.50	72.50			

Overview of Reviews:		EDyMCE-Nord			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Yvon Besanger-Moleres</i>	<i>Katja Sirviö</i>	<i>Evangelos Rikos</i>	<i>Alkistis Kontou</i>		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	9	8	8		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	10	7	8	9		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	10	6	8	10		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	10	7	8	10		
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	9	8	7		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	84.38	95.00	72.50	80.00	90.00		

Overview of Reviews:		RECORD			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Heybet</i>	<i>Arjen</i>	<i>Trevor</i>	<i>Davide</i>		
		<i>Kilic</i>	<i>Jongepier</i>	<i>Hardy</i>	<i>Fioriti</i>		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	10	7	9		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	6	3	8		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	6	8	6	9		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	8	5	8		
General quality of the proposal	25%	6	7	4	9		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	65.63	60.00	72.50	45.00	85.00		

Overview of Reviews:		OS-DGApp			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Reza</i>	<i>Pedro</i>	<i>Kalle</i>			
		<i>Arghandeh</i>	<i>Nardelli</i>	<i>Rauma</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	10	6			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	7	6			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	7	8			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	5	6	5			
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	8	6			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	65.83	65.00	70.00	62.50			

Overview of Reviews:		BN			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Petr</i>	<i>Theofilos</i>	<i>Ian</i>	<i>Andreas</i>	<i>Geraint</i>	
		<i>Toman</i>	<i>Papadopoulos</i>	<i>Gilbert</i>	<i>Kyprianou</i>	<i>Chaffey</i>	
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		9	7	7	6	4	
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	5	8	8	7	
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	7	8	8	6	
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	6	6	8	6	
General quality of the proposal	25%	9	5	9	8	8	
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	72.5	80.00	57.50	77.50	80.00	67.50	

Overview of Reviews:		DIAPROCON			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>João Francisco</i>	<i>Rafael</i>	<i>Erik</i>			
		<i>Alves Martins</i>	<i>Pena-Alzola</i>	<i>de Jong</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	7	9			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	8	8			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	8	6			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	8	8	5			
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	10	8			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	77.5	80.00	85.00	67.50			

Overview of Reviews:		FLUCCOM			APPROVED		
		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
Questions		<i>Ulf Håger</i>	<i>Iñaki Orue</i>	<i>Mihaela Albu</i>	<i>Santiago Sánchez Acevedo</i>		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	8	8	10		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	9	7	4	7		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	8	6	9		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	8	7	5	8		
General quality of the proposal	25%	9	8	3	9		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	71.88	85.00	75.00	45.00	82.50		

Overview of Reviews:		ORCA			APPROVED		
		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
Questions		<i>Filip Prööstl Andrén</i>	<i>Evangelos Rikos</i>	<i>Sebastian Rohjans</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	7	5			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	7	9	9			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	9	8			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	8	9	7			
General quality of the proposal	25%	7	8	9			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	80.83	72.50	87.50	82.50			

Overview of Reviews:		DESIRE			APPROVED		
		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
Questions		<i>Murat Gol</i>	<i>Hannu Laaksonen</i>	<i>Mohamed Shalaby</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		9	7	8			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	5	7	9			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	6	6	9			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	6	8			
General quality of the proposal	25%	7	7	9			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	71.67	62.50	65.00	87.50			

Overview of Reviews:		EVGFC			APPROVED		
		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
Questions		<i>Jose Maria Maza-Ortega</i>	<i>Alkistis Kontou</i>	<i>Salvador Ceballos</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	10	7			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	9	9	8			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	9	10	9			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	9	9	7			
General quality of the proposal	25%	9	8	7			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	85.83	90.00	90.00	77.50			

4.3.11 Evaluation of 11th Call Proposals

The following list shows the evaluation results of the 11th call.

Overview of Reviews:		PIEMgrid			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>João Francisco</i>	<i>Yvon</i>	<i>Erik</i>			
		<i>Alves Martins</i>	<i>Besanger-Moleres</i>	<i>de Jong</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	8	10			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	7	9	10			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	6	8	10			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	5	8	8			
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	8	10			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		80.83	65.00	82.50			

Overview of Reviews:		DGNet				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Spyros</i>	<i>Jose Maria</i>	<i>Ata</i>	<i>Mihaela</i>	<i>Manuel</i>	
		<i>Skarvelis-Kazakos</i>	<i>Maza-Ortega</i>	<i>Khavari</i>	<i>Albu</i>	<i>Barragan-Villarejo</i>	
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		9	9	8	10	9	
Scientific/technical merit	25%	7	9	8	9	9	
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	9	7	9	9	
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	5	9	8	9	7	
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	9	8	9	9	
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		82.5	70.00	90.00	77.50	90.00	85.00

Overview of Reviews:		ACROPOLIS				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Davood</i>	<i>Artjoms</i>	<i>Van Hoa</i>	<i>Joern</i>		
		<i>Babazadeh</i>	<i>Obusevs</i>	<i>Nguyen</i>	<i>Geisbuesch</i>		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	8	10	9		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	5	8	8	6		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	5	8	6	3		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	5	10	7	6		
General quality of the proposal	25%	5	8	8	5		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		64.38	50.00	85.00	72.50	50.00	

Overview of Reviews:		ORICSµg			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Luca Ferrarini</i>	<i>Hannu Laaksonen</i>	<i>Marialaura Di Somma</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		9	8	9			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	5	4	5			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	6	5	6			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	4	4			
General quality of the proposal	25%	6	4	5			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	50	57.50	42.50	50.00			

Overview of Reviews:		DRIMPC-Stability			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Evangelos Rikos</i>	<i>Alkistis Kontou</i>	<i>Davide Fioriti</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	8	8			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	5	8			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	6	8			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	9	5	7			
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	4	8			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	70	82.50	50.00	77.50			

4.3.12 Evaluation of 12th Call Proposals

The following list shows the evaluation results of the 12th call.

Overview of Reviews:		CAILIM			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>J. Emilio Rodriguez-Seco</i>	<i>Georg Lauss</i>	<i>Mihaela Albu</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	6	9			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	9	8	10			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	7	9			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	7	9			
General quality of the proposal	25%	9	7	10			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	83.33	82.50	72.50	95.00			

Overview of Reviews:		TS-HVDC			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Davood Babazadeh</i>	<i>Alkistis Kontou</i>	<i>Erik de Jong</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	10	9			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	9	9			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	9	10	9			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	9	9	8			
General quality of the proposal	25%	10	10	9			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	90.83	90.00	95.00	87.50			

Overview of Reviews:		REMOTEC			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Heybet Kilic</i>	<i>Alkistis Kontou</i>	<i>Trevor Hardy</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	4	5			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	9	7			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	6	10	6			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	8	6			
General quality of the proposal	25%	6	9	8			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	74.17	65.00	90.00	67.50			

Overview of Reviews:		SMART-DROOP			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Diana Strauss-Mincu</i>	<i>Ian Gilbert</i>	<i>Aggelos Bouhouras</i>	<i>Marialaura Di Somma</i>		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	6	9	7		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	7	7	8	6		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	7	8	7		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	7	7	5		
General quality of the proposal	25%	6	7	4	6		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	65.63	65.00	70.00	67.50	60.00		

Overview of Reviews:		HEMSVRT			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Georg Lauss</i>	<i>Evangelos Rikos</i>	<i>Venizelos Efthymiou</i>	<i>Ibrahim Abdulhadi</i>	<i>Konstantinos Kotsalos</i>	
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	8	9	6	10	
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	8	10	8	9	
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	8	9	7	9	
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	8	8	7	9	
General quality of the proposal	25%	7	9	10	9	9	
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)	81.5	65.00	82.50	92.50	77.50	90.00	

4.3.13 Evaluation of 13th Call Proposals

The following list shows the evaluation results of the 13th call.

Overview of Reviews:		WASIPS			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Heybet</i> <i>Kilic</i>	<i>Georg</i> <i>Lauss</i>	<i>Mihaela</i> <i>Albu</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	8	8			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	6	8			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	6	7	8			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	6	8			
General quality of the proposal	25%	6	7	9			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		69.17	60.00	65.00			

Overview of Reviews:		oZmLib61850			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Ulf</i> <i>Häger</i>	<i>Jose Maria</i> <i>Maza-Ortega</i>	<i>Georg</i> <i>Lauss</i>	<i>Evangelos</i> <i>Rikos</i>	<i>Alkistis</i> <i>Kontou</i>	
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		6	6	8	8	9	
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	8	7	9	8	
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	9	8	8	9	8	
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	8	8	7	9	8	
General quality of the proposal	25%	9	9	8	9	6	
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		81.5	85.00	82.50	90.00	75.00	

Overview of Reviews:		LIVABLE-LV			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Theofilos</i> <i>Papadopoulos</i>	<i>Georg</i> <i>Lauss</i>	<i>Santiago</i> <i>Sánchez Acevedo</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	8	9			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	8	6			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	7	7			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	5	6	5			
General quality of the proposal	25%	7	7	8			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		65.83	62.50	70.00			

Overview of Reviews:		DARC PV			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Roland Bründlinger</i>	<i>Mohamed Shalaby</i>	<i>Ian Gilbert</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	6	8			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	9	6			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	8	6			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	9	7			
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	9	6			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		75.83	77.50	62.50			

Overview of Reviews:		RENEWIES			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Nand Kishor</i>	<i>Spyros Skarvelis-Kazakos</i>	<i>Evangelos Rikos</i>	<i>Trevor Hardy</i>		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	8	8	4		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	4	6	8	3		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	2	7	8	2		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	4	9	9	5		
General quality of the proposal	25%	4	7	9	1		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		55	35.00	72.50	27.50		

Overview of Reviews:		QUINPORTION			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Murat Gol</i>	<i>Davood Babazadeh</i>	<i>Joern Geisbuesch</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	10	8			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	9	9	7			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	9	4			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	8	7	8			
General quality of the proposal	25%	9	9	6			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		77.5	85.00	62.50			

Overview of Reviews:		ForDis			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Alkistis Kontou</i>	<i>Salvatore D'Arco</i>	<i>Manuel Barragan-Villarejo</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	10	10			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	8	6			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	7	8			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	6	7			
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	8	7			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		73.33	77.50	72.50	70.00		

Overview of Reviews:		5G-SmartPV			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Luca Ferrarini	Pedro Nardelli	Georg Lauss			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	9	8			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	5	8	4			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	6	8	3			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	9	4			
General quality of the proposal	25%	6	9	1			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		57.5	85.00	30.00			

Overview of Reviews:		HyMiCO-RPC			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Georg Lauss	Evangelos Rikos	Anna Kulmala			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	8	7			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	7	8	3			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	8	4			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	7	5			
General quality of the proposal	25%	7	8	3			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		61.67	70.00	77.50			

Overview of Reviews:		AESI-HM			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Yvon Besanger-Moleres	Arjen Jongepier	Hannu Laaksonen			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	8	8			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	7	6			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	7	7			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	7	6			
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	7	7			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		70	75.00	70.00			

Overview of Reviews:		BiFlow-HMG			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		Van Hoa Nguyen	Georg Lauss	Davide Fioriti			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	10	8			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	5	8	3			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	6	8	5			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	7	4			
General quality of the proposal	25%	5	8	2			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		55.83	77.50	35.00			

Overview of Reviews:		AID4RISC-V-EPES				APPROVED	
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Davood Babazadeh</i>	<i>Filip Pröbstl Andrén</i>	<i>Sebastian Rohjans</i>	<i>Carlo Tomelli</i>		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	8	7	8		
Scientific/technical merit	25%	9	8	9	9		
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	9	8	10	8		
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	8	7	9	7		
General quality of the proposal	25%	9	9	9	9		
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		85.63	87.50	80.00	92.50	82.50	

Overview of Reviews:		MCR			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Thomas I. Strasser</i>	<i>J. Emilio Rodriguez-Seco</i>	<i>Georg Lauss</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	8	10			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	8	9			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	8	9			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	7	8			
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	9	9			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		81.67	77.50	80.00	87.50		

Overview of Reviews:		HyStorization			APPROVED		
Questions		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5	Review 6
		<i>Thomas I. Strasser</i>	<i>J. Emilio Rodriguez-Seco</i>	<i>Georg Lauss</i>			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		6	7	8			
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	7	8			
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	8	8			
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	7	6			
General quality of the proposal	25%	7	8	7			
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100)		74.17	75.00	75.00	72.50		

5 Lab Access User Workshops

As part of the dissemination actions in ERIGrid 2.0, two user workshops⁴ have been organised during the project to present the lab access project results, and facilitate the exchange and feedback within the user groups, with consortium members and other stakeholders.

The first user workshop was an event held online on 20th October 2023. It was organised as a mini-conference with the corresponding proceedings and presentations (Rodriguez et al., 2023) available on Zenodo⁵. A first group of exemplary user projects were selected for presentation to an international audience, sharing experiences and problems found during the access process and at the lab implementations. 75 people had registered, and 65 finally attended. The agenda is presented in Figure 4.

The figure shows a slide titled "1st User Workshop Mini Conference" with the ERIGrid 2.0 logo. It lists an agenda of activities from 9:30 to 12:00. The activities include opening remarks, six user group presentations with Q&A sessions, a coffee break, and a summary closing. Each activity lists the time, the user group or topic, and the host lab.

Time	Activity	Host Lab
9:30-9:40	Opening Remarks	Thomas Strasser (AIT), J. Emilio Rodriguez (TECNALIA)
9:40-9:55	User Group 1: Cyber attack in PV system for voltage regulation in distribution network (CybTEST)	Seema Yadav, User Group: Motilal Nehru National Institute of Technology (MNNIT) Allahabad (India)
9:55-10:00	Q&A	Host Lab: IntelligentEnergy Testbed (VTT), Finland
10:00-10:15	User Group 2: Performance Analysis of PV Integrated Distribution Network with combination of Different Control Strategies and Communication Network (PERFECT)	Anju Yadav, User Group: Motilal Nehru National Institute of Technology (MNNIT) Allahabad (India)
10:15-10:20	Q&A	Host Lab: IntelligentEnergy Testbed (VTT), Finland
10:20-10:35	User Group 3: Wavelet-Transform based Signal Processing for the Validation of Power Flow Tracing Approach (COLOURPOWER)	Eduardo Vega Fuentes, User Group: University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (Spain) and University of Glasgow (UK)
10:35-10:40	Q&A	Host Lab: Distributed Energy Resources Test Facility (RSE), Italy
10:35-10:45	Coffee Break	
10:45-11:00	User Group 4: Power Hardware-in-the-Loop Testing of Single-Phase Grid-Forming VSCs in Grid-Connected Mode (PHIL-1phGFVSC)	Manuel Barragán Villarejo, Francisco Jesús Matas Díaz, User Group: University of Sevilla (Spain)
11:00-11:05	Q&A	Host Lab: Electric Energy Systems Laboratory (ICCS-NTUA), Greece
11:05-11:20	User Group 5: Coordinating residential flexibility resources in a socio-technical co-simulation design (CO-FLEX)	Matteo Barsanti, User Group: The École polytechnique fédérale de Lausanne (Switzerland)
11:20-11:25	Q&A	Host Lab: SESA-Lab (OFFIS), Germany
11:25-11:40	User Group 6: Intelligent Control to Enhance Power Smoothing of DERs based Microgrid (IC2PSofMG)	User Group: Dicle University (Turkey), Shahid Rajaei Teacher Training University (Iran)
11:40-11:45	Q&A	Host Lab: Distributed Generation Laboratory (CRES), Greece
11:45-12:00	Summary Closing Remarks	Ibrahim Abdulhadi (Univ. of Strathclyde), Santiago Sanchez Acevedo (SINTEF)

Figure 4: Agenda of the 1st lab access user workshop.

⁴<https://erigrd2.eu/user-workshops/>

⁵<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8414625>

The second user workshop was organised at the end of the project, integrated within the ERI-Grid 2.0 Final Event held face-to-face in Vienna on 1st April 2025. The Session “Facilitating Effective Laboratory Testing by Lab Users” has been moderated by the ERIGrid 2.0 Lab Access Manager, who started with an introduction and main achievements of the Lab Access Programme deployed for 4.5 years.

Around 90 international experts followed the presentations of 6 user groups on their latest investigations, results, and practical experiences in the ERIGrid 2.0 RI when implementing in the different labs the following projects: *EDyMCE-Nord*, *iniTiate*, *DGNet*, *ProMiSe*, *WindGrid*, *DeMaDsVal*, *FaultS*, *HVLD*, and *RCPIN*.

The image shows a slide titled "ERIGRID 2.0 Final Event 1 April 2025, Vienna, AT". The slide lists the agenda for the session "Facilitating Effective Laboratory Testing by Lab Users (2nd User Workshop)".

Session "Facilitating Effective Laboratory Testing by Lab Users (2 nd User Workshop)" (Moderator: J. Emilio Rodriguez)	
13:00 – 13:40	Overview and Achievements of the Access Program (TECNALIA – J. Emilio Rodriguez, RWTH – Andres Acosta)
13:40 – 14:00	Lab Access Project 1 "Expansion of the initial Dynamic Model of CE with the Nordic power system and implementation on OPAL-RT's ePHASORsim" (ZHAW – Miguel Ramirez, Artjoms Obusevs)
14:00 – 14:20	Lab Access Project 2 "Measurement-based modelling, dynamic analysis and control of active distribution networks: the iniTiate, DGNet and ProMiSe projects" (DUTH – Theofilos Papadopoulos)
14:20 – 14:40	Lab Access Project 3 "Wind power plants in dynamic states of the power grid" (AGH – Tomasz Lerch)
14:40 – 15:00	Lab Access Project 4 "Data Driven Detection of Malfunctioning Devices in Power Distribution Systems Validation" (FHTW/AIT – David Fellner)
15:00 – 15:30	Coffee break
15:30 – 15:50	Lab Access Project 5 "Fault Detection, Classification and Location in Distribution Networks: The FaultS and HVLD projects" (ENEIDA.IO – Guilherme Freire)
15:50 – 16:10	Lab Access Project 6 "Resilient Power Inverter Network: A Hardware-in-the-Loop Simulation Case Study" (KTH – Henrik Sandberg)

Figure 5: Agenda of the 2nd lab access user workshop.

Figure 6 shows a few pictures of diverse presentations of the Session, jointly with a group photo of the attendees.

Similar to the 1st user workshop, for the 2nd workshop a booklet and presentations (Rodriguez et al., 2025) have been made publicly available through Zenodo⁶.

⁶<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15004521>

Figure 6: Photographs of the 2nd ERIGrid 2.0 lab access user workshop held in Vienna.

6 Provision of Lab Access

6.1 Summary of Lab Access Achievements and Outlook

As mentioned, the lab access programme in ERIGrid 2.0 has launched 13 calls for user proposals from October 2020 to September 2024, allowing the project implementations in the lab until April 2025. The provision of access at the project level can be summarised in the following main points and the related Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) in Figure 7:

- 147 proposals received.
- 106 projects implemented in the labs:
 - 1,677 access days (i.e., 102% of 1,650 access days, final objective indicated in the Grant Agreement (*ERIGrid 2.0 Grant Agreement*, 2019)).
 - 224 users coming from universities, research organisations, industries, and other organisations.
 - 19 industrial projects (i.e., projects with the lead or participation of industries): 18% of the total projects.
 - 370 access days provided to users from non-EU organisations: 22% of the total provided access days.
 - 191 access days corresponding to ERIGrid 2.0 partners (“internal lab access”): 11% of the total access.
 - Out of 1,677 access days, 288 access days have been provided in remote mode, i.e., the experiment was running the laboratory with the user group following it remotely.

Lab Access KPIs	PROVIDED ACCESS (accepted completed projects)	%	LIMIT / OBJECTIVE
Access Days	1677	102%	1650
Remote Access Days	288	17%	
Users	224	83%	269
User Projects	106	80%	133
Non-EU Access Days	370	22%	< 20%
Remote Non-EU Access Days	17	5%	
Industrial Projects	19	18%	>25%
Industrial Access Days	284	17%	
Internal Lab Access Days	191	11%	< 10%
Multi-lab Projects	3		---

Note: Relevant KPIs are those in yellow background. Those in white background are only for indicative purposes.

Figure 7: ERIGrid 2.0 Lab Access KPIs.

Concerning the user projects which were not implemented in the lab, the analysis can be summarised in the following main points:

- 11 proposals have not been approved by the USP (92.5% acceptance ratio).
- 10 proposals have not been accepted due to the “non-EU limit” (the access to be provided to users coming from non-EU countries was limited to 20% of the total access).

- 5 proposals have not been feasible to be implemented in the lab for technical or economic reasons.
- 15 proposals have been withdrawn by the users despite being accepted by the USP and were feasible in the labs.

6.2 Degree of Access Provision

Further to the overall numbers of the previous section, this section describes in more detail the provision of lab access and the degree of accomplishment of the individual commitments by the ERIGrid 2.0 partners.

The Grant Agreement (*ERIGrid 2.0 Grant Agreement*, 2019) states the minimum quantity of access to be provided by each installation in terms of access days. Figure 8 presents the initial values and includes an estimation of the corresponding number of user projects and users linked to the access days.

Access provider short name	Short name of infrastructure	Installation		Installation Country code	Type of access	Unit of access	Unit cost (UC) (€)	Min. quantity of access to be provided	Access costs		Estimated number of users	Estimated number of user projects
		No	Short name						On the basis of UC	As actual costs		
AIT	SmartEST-Lab	1	SmartEST	AT	TA-ac	day		200		147.500,00	32	14
CRES	PV&DGLab	3	PV&DGLab	GR	TA-uc	day	1.203,47	80	96.277,60		14	7
DTU	PowerlabDK	4	SYSLAB/ESSL	DK	TA-ac	day		80		160.700,00	16	8
TUD	ESE-Lab	6	ESE-Lab	NL	TA-uc	day	1.990,00	60	119.400,00		10	5
KEMA	FPGL	7	FPGL	NL	TA-uc	day	6.875,00	20	137.500,00		8	4
IEE	SysTec	8	SysTec	DE	TA-ac	day		75	138.635,95		10	5
HEDNO	L&RS-lab	9	L&RS-lab	GR	TA-uc	day	518,38	15	7.775,70		4	2
HEDNO	SGC-LAB	10	SGC-LAB	GR	TA-uc	day	585,00	10	5.850,00		4	2
ICCS	EFS-lab	12	EFS-lab	GR	TA-uc	day	1.800,67	108	194.469,12		16	8
JRC	SGILab	14	SGILAB-PTT	NL	TA-ac	day		100		91.250,00	14	7
JRC	SGILab	15	SGILAB-IPR	IT	TA-ac	day		100		91.250,00	14	7
OFFIS	SESA-Lab	16	SESA-Lab	DE	TA-ac	day		75		81.875,00	10	5
OCT	UDEX	18	UDEX	ES	TA-uc	day	5.638,08	40	225.522,40		10	5
RSE	DER-TF	19	DER-TF	IT	TA-uc	day	2.762,00	75	207.150,00		16	8
RWTH	RTlab	21	RTlab	DE	TA-ac	day		120		94.365,00	12	6
SINTEF	NSGL	23	NSGL	NO	TA-ac	day		105		144.331,25	14	7
TECNALIA	SGTL	24	SGTL	ES	TA-ac	day		100		102.187,50	15	6
UCY	LVEM	25	LVEM	CY	TA-ac	day		100		75.000,00	10	5
UoS	DPSL	26	DPSL	UK	TA-uc	day	1.494,83	50	74.741,50		10	5
UoS	PNDC	27	PNDC	UK	TA-uc	day	3.120,00	55	171.600,00		10	5
VTT	MultiPower	29	MultiPower	FI	TA-ac	day		125		124.717,50	20	10
Total								1.693			269	133

Figure 8: Provision of access as stated in the Grant Agreement of ERIGrid 2.0.

During ERIGrid 2.0, the individual lab performance in terms of lab access has been closely monitored. To use the project total budget allocated for lab access as efficiently as possible and maximise the overall number of access days at the project level, three budget shifts have been implemented from “less successful” to “more successful” partners. As a result, the minimum quantity of access to be provided per partner has changed. The latest values are included in Figure 9.

The distribution of lab access days provided by each partner concerning the goals included in the Grant Agreement (*ERIGrid 2.0 Grant Agreement*, 2019) is shown in Figure 10.

Figure 11 represents the same information jointly with the total figures at the project/consortium level.

6.3 Access Provision per User Organisation Country

A large number of countries have used the opportunity offered by ERIGrid 2.0 to the research community. An analysis of the countries of the user organisations that have benefited from getting access to the RIs has been carried out for each researcher. It shows Germany as the

Access provider short name	Short name of infrastructure	NEW CONTRACT: Min. Number of access days to be provided
AIT	SmartEST Lab	215
CRES	PV&DGLab	80
DTU	PowerlabDK	91
TUD	ESE-Lab	60
KEMA	FPGL	20
IEE	SysTec	65
HEDNO	L&RS-lab	0
HEDNO	SGC-LAB	0
ICCS	EES-lab	130
JRC	SGILab-PTT	5
JRC	SGILab-IPR	73
OFFIS	SESA-Lab	75
OCT	UDEX	40
RSE	DER-TF	75
RWTH	RTlab	122
SINTEF	NSGL	146
TECNALIA	SGTL	100
UCY	LVEM	27
UoS	DPSL	100
UoS	PNDC	65
VTT	MultiPower	125
TOTAL ERIGrid 2.0		1650

Figure 9: Updated provision of access after budget shifts between partners.

Figure 10: Lab access provided by installation.

dominant country, followed by India (non-EU), Turkey (Associated Country), Spain and Italy, as presented in Figures 12 and 13. Please note that what is considered is not the nationality of the users but the country where their organisations are located.

Figure 11: Number of access days provided: total and by installation.

Figure 12: Access distribution by country of the user organisation (bar chart representation).

Organization country of each individual user	Nº Access days	Nº of users
Germany	357	27
India	257	16
Turkey	224	19
Spain	211	19
Italy	183	21
Greece	130	12
Poland	125	10
UK	124	14
Belgium	108	6
France	79	6
Switzerland	74	9
Pakistan	68	2
Finland	64	4
Colombia	63	2
Portugal	60	12
Norway	57	7
Malta	52	3
Denmark	44	3
Cyprus	40	4
Croatia	39	3
Austria	39	3
Sweden	38	3
South Africa	32	2
Japan	30	3
The Netherlands	30	2
Iran	30	2
USA	25	2
Jordan	24	3
Estonia	24	1
Romania	24	1
Brazil	20	1
Egypt	10	1
Canada	2	1
	2911	224

Figure 13: Access distribution by country of the user organisation (table representation).

7 Provision of Virtual Access

Unlike ERIGrid⁷, the ERIGrid 2.0 project provides the opportunity to access virtual infrastructures to researchers around the world. This VA is made available free of charge for open and freely available resources such as databases, real-time data or simulation platforms. It aims to facilitate casual online access with minimal administrative overhead compared to the more elaborate application and selection process defined in the lab access procedure described in previous sections. In the VA modality, there is no need to submit a proposal, there is no competitive selection of the users through the USP, and there is no mandatory technical report foreseen after the access.

During the ERIGrid 2.0 project, 10 virtual facilities were operating and could be reached on the ERIGrid 2.0 web page⁸. Figure 14 shows the offered VA services.

Figure 14: Virtual access facilities offered by ERIGrid 2.0.

Deliverable D6.1 (*D-NA5.1 Specification of the Trans-national Access and Virtual Access Programmes*, 2021) provides further description of these virtual facilities, the access procedure, and some associated ancillary tools used to support and monitor these services. The VA is assessed every 18 months by a board of international experts, except for the last assessment, which took place 25 months after the second one, due to the ERIGrid 2.0 project's extension. The periodic evaluations have been formalised in Deliverable D6.2 (*D-NA5.2a Virtual Access Assessment Report*, 2021), Deliverable D6.3 (*D-NA5.2b Virtual Access Assessment Report*, 2023), and Deliverable D6.4 (*D-NA5.2c Virtual Access Assessment Report*, 2025).

The access to the VA infrastructures is not measured as it is in the typical lab access (in terms of “access days” spent in the lab). There is no unit of access defined but some metrics and statistics are collected on the VA activity; quantity of use, geographical distribution of users, etc. ERIGrid 2.0 has implemented web analytic services for users visiting the VA facilities based on the open-source tool Matomo⁹.

⁷<https://erigrd.eu>

⁸<https://erigrd2.eu/lab-access>

⁹<https://matomo.org>

7.1 Web Analytics

The data presented in this section has been collected by the web-tracking tool Matomo during a period starting at the beginning of the ERIGrid 2.0 project (April 2020) and ending by March 2025.

Table 2 ranks the services according to the number of page views and unique visitors. A direct comparison among VA services based on these numbers is not justified, as not all services have been online at the same time during this analysis period. From the total number of visits to the ERIGrid 2.0 web site, 20% correspond to visits to the VA services.

Table 2: Overview of Matomo web-analytics visitors and page-views.

Partner	Facility	Unique Visitors	Page-views
—	ERIGrid 2.0 Mainpage	45,344	131,076
—	VA Support Forum	1,123	2,626
—	VA User Questionnaire	1,201	2,971
ICCS	OpenAFPM	6,550	32,982
UoS	Smartgrid MVP	1,788	3,186
OFFIS	SESA Virt. SIM	1,142	1,481
HEDNO	SGRID	889	1,174
RSE	DER-TF DaaS	691	2,208
RWTH	Vlab	619	1,656
ICCS	Virtual Lab	173	576
DTU	SYSLAB VA	108	189
AIT	SmartEST Sim Lab	76	133
Sum VA		12,036	43,585
Sum All		59,704	180,258

Figure 15 and Figure 16 show the geographical origin of the users who visited the ERIGrid 2.0 VA services. There is a clear participation of countries from all continents and especially from the USA and Asia. The percentage of visitors located in European countries is 58,6%. Figure 17 shows the number of unique visitors gathered by the Matomo web analytics tool during the analysed period, and compares it with the visitors obtained through the user questionnaire.

From these data, it was estimated that around 8% of the lab access visitors accessed the VA services. In addition, three important peaks can be seen in October 2020, which correlate with the joint ERIGrid 2.0/PANTERA webinar/workshop in which the VA programme was especially covered, in February 2021, and in December 2023.

Figure 15: Origins of users based on their IP address (Matomo analytics).

Figure 16: Origins of users within the EU based on their IP address (Matomo analytics).

Figure 17: Unique visitor numbers over time for VA services.

Figure 18 lists the social networks which were used to promote the ERIGrid 2.0 services.

Figure 18: Social networks used to promote VA services.

Figure 19 shows the number of visits per unique visitor. It can be seen that there is an important number of recurrent users of the VA infrastructures.

7.2 User Questionnaire Inputs

In addition to the automatically collected statistics by the Matomo web analytics tool, VA users are asked to provide additional details voluntarily before accessing the VA service of interest. This is done using a web form, namely the user questionnaire. In the reporting period, 1213 users have provided this information. From this list, unique email accounts were filtered out, and users who were part of the ERIGrid 2.0 project were removed to get an estimate of the unique number of users, resulting in a value of 301. Since users can decide not to fill out the user questionnaire, and also because once they are redirected to the VA service platform, they don't need to fill out the questionnaire again, this estimate only represents a lower bound. Moreover, comparing it with the total number of users of the lab access programme (224, see

Figure 19: Number of visits by visitors based on their IP address (Matomo analytics).

Figures 12 and 13), it is possible to confirm the potential that the VA service has to reach a broader community.

Figure 20 shows the distribution of the users between the available VA services. Figure 21 shows the distribution of countries from which users come based on their inputs provided.

Figure 20: Distribution of users between services gathered via questionnaire.

Figure 22 shows the distribution of these countries after classifying them in EU and non-EU countries. EU users represent 43% of the total. Figure 22b shows the number of users coming from an academic institution vs. from the industry. The majority of users have an academic background. Industrial users represent 14% of the total. As shown in Figure 23, this share rises to 24% if only EU users are considered.

Figure 21: Distribution of user home countries gathered via questionnaire.

Figure 22: Distribution of user origins gathered via questionnaire.

7.3 Up-time Monitoring

Figure 24 shows the dashboard¹⁰ of the ERIGrid 2.0 services. This dashboard is accessible to the public and lists all monitored services with their current state and past incidents. Periods of unavailability are indicated by red bars, while periods of proper operation are marked in green. Periods of prolonged downtime, such as, for example, for the UoS Live Grid MVP or DTU SYSLAB VA, can be explained by platform upgrades like data storage updates and the implementation of new internal Application Programming Interfaces (APIs).

¹⁰<https://stats.uptimebot.com/LBVOxFkNWN>

Figure 23: Distribution of European users by institution type.

Figure 24: UptimeRobot service dashboard.

8 Conclusions

Built on the lessons learned from its predecessor project, the ERIGrid 2.0 Lab Access Programme has been defined and deployed over the past 4.5 years, including a set of VA services.

Improvement and significant progress have been achieved in ERIGrid 2.0 compared to the predecessor project ERIGrid: 147 user proposals have been received (versus 97 in ERIGrid) in 13 calls (vs. 6 calls in ERIGrid). As a result, 224 users (vs. 175) have had access to the laboratories for implementing 106 projects (vs. 73) during 1,677 access days (vs. 1,038 in ERIGrid). The success of ERIGrid has been consolidated and extended in ERIGrid 2.0 in a way that has even surpassed the very challenging initial objective (1,650 access days).

This outstanding performance could be accomplished despite the COVID-19 pandemic restrictions that affected the project during the first two years. The greater flexibility of access provision by laboratories, the possibility of remote access, and the simplification and automation of part of the administrative process have compensated for the initial delays and inconveniences.

ERIGrid 2.0 continued the support to the research community when trying to validate smart grid and smart energy system configurations in the lab before field deployment. The focus was mainly on user organisations in Europe but also outside (around 20% of total access), with special mention to the huge acceptance in India (without a clear reason detected). In general, the feedback received from the user groups was very positive, and many success stories and good outcomes could be reported.

Two user workshops have been organised with the presentation of a selection of user projects in a great networking atmosphere, where feedback has been exchanged between users and stakeholders.

As happened in ERIGrid, it turned out that the consortium had difficulties in attracting industrial users (only 18% of the total number of user projects involved the participation of industries, below the 25% target): potential confidentiality issues and timing of the access process (proposal preparation, evaluation, etc.) could be perceived as drawbacks by this type of organisation.

As a novelty in ERIGrid 2.0, in addition to the access to a wide range of experimental facilities, 10 VA services (on-line databases, real-time data and simulation platforms) have been made freely available to users as a helpful complement with minimal administrative overheads (i.e., no submitted proposal, no evaluation, no final report).

In conclusion, the ERIGrid 2.0 project offered a wide variety of facilities and services for the testing and validation of smart energy systems, covering a broad range of technologies. Users could benefit from the testing infrastructure combined with the know-how of experienced laboratory staff members to improve their developments and gain valuable input for the progress of their methods and product design.

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Appendix: Proposal Review Report

An example of a Proposal Review Report is presented in this section. The proposal/project data have been anonymised (call number, proposal reference, proposal acronym and user group organisation). Reviewers' names have always been anonymous to the user. In the review report the individual scores provided by the involved USP experts are stated per category jointly with their specific comments and suggestions for improvement.

The Proposal Review Report was sent by email by the ERIGrid 2.0 proposal submission system¹¹ (ConfTool-based) once the proposal had been assessed by the USP and accepted by the ERIGrid 2.0 Project Coordination and Management Team.

```

=====
From: ERIGrid 2.0 Consortium <erigrd2@conftool.net>
Sent on: XXXXXXXX
To: XXXXXXXXXXXXX
CC: XXXXXXXXXXXXX
Subject: [ERIGrid 2.0] Lab Access (Xth Call): User Proposal Evaluation Results
=====
  
```

Dear XXXXXXXXX,

We would like to inform you that your Lab Access user proposal "<Title of the proposal>" (ERIGrid 2.0 Reference: XXX) has been evaluated by the ERIGrid 2.0 User Selection Panel, with the following review details:

PROPOSAL DETAILS

ID: XXX
 Proposal: <Title of the proposal>

REVIEW RESULT OF THE USER SELECTION PANEL: This contribution has been accepted.

The assigned lab is "Distributed Energy Resources Test Facility (RSE)".

Please get in contact with the assigned lab through the lab enquiry form or the provided contact information at <https://erigrd2.eu/lab-access/> in order to confirm the feasibility of your project in the lab and organize your stay there.

OVERVIEW OF REVIEWS

Review 1

=====

Evaluation of the Proposal

Merit (25%): 8
 Improve know-how (25%): 9
 Compliance (25%): 7
 General quality (25%): 9
 Total points (out of 100): 83

¹¹<https://conftool.net/erigrd2>

Comments for the Authors

The project proposal is very well prepared, the target is clearly defined and the process is described step by step in details. The expected results would be beneficial for the community.

The question could be if the proposed techniques/items to simulate failure modes are really faithfully corresponding with real PV failures. Probably some work was done but it is not directly referenced in the first part of chapter 3 where the items for failure simulation are introduced.

According my opinion the comparison with real failures could be done before. There should be possible collect panels with developing failures which are able test.

On other side the proposed techniques to simulate failure modes are corresponding with expected behavior of PV panel with faults described from physics point of view.

I recommend the proposal for acceptance.

Review 2

=====

Evaluation of the Proposal

Merit (25%): 6

Improve know-how (25%): 7

Compliance (25%): 7

General quality (25%): 9

Total points (out of 100): 73

Comments for the Authors

The proposal deals with a topic, of reliability and efficient O&M of PV systems, which is of a high priority at a EU level and it is also in-line with the ERIGRID2.0 research area.

The description of the proposal is very informative and of a good quality. The proposal tries to use datasets from a simulated behavior of PV modules representing aging and failure mechanisms, in order to train failure detection and diagnosis (FDD) algorithms. For procedures simulating aging there is always a concern about how close to real conditions this simulation is. It would be interesting to investigate the validity and comparison of the patterns found in the datasets of this simulated operation with datasets from the field operation PV systems, in this or in a future work.

The proposal will improve the know-how and capacities of two labs of the ERIGRID2.0, through the involvement of two important partners and the mutual benefits from synergies.

Review 3

=====

Evaluation of the Proposal

Merit (25%): 9

Improve know-how (25%): 10

Compliance (25%): 10

General quality (25%): 9

Total points (out of 100): 95

Comments for the Authors

It is very good project. I would recommend it.

In case of questions do not hesitate to contact us at access@erigrd2.eu.

Best regards,

Your ERIGrid 2.0 Team

—

ERIGrid 2.0

<https://www.conftool.net/erigrd2/>

Consortium

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